

THE QUESTION OF UNIVERSALS IN ETHNOBIOLOGICAL NOMENCLATURE: RE-EXAMINATION WITH SOUTHEAST ASIAN LINGUISTIC DATA

The classification and naming of plants and animals is said to follow a number of “universal” constraints cross-linguistically. While these constraints are generally accepted in the literature, few have been rigorously tested with a large language sample. In particular, the languages of mainland southeast Asia appear to have been neglected in such endeavours, even though it is common knowledge that some key constraints are violated in this region. Here, we investigate the construction of “Generic” plant and animal names in 22 languages of mainland southeast Asia, and show that the vast majority of these – especially among plant and fish ethnotaxa – are two-part “secondary names”, in contrast to a major constraint that predicts that such names should be one-part “primary names”. This appears to be a widespread areal feature, and has implications for the validity of other nomenclatural “universals”, which remain to be similarly tested.

Austroasiatic, Kra-Dai, Tibeto-Burman, ethnoclassification, Brent Berlin, Life Form

1. INTRODUCTION

The existence of cross-linguistic universals in the ethnobiological classification systems of the world’s cultures has been a hotly debated topic for a number of decades. In his seminal work based primarily on the languages of Central and South America, Brent Berlin (1992) proposed a model that made very strong predictions about not only the manner in which people categorise the living organisms around them, but also the nomenclature (*i.e.* linguistic labels) of the resulting groupings. Around the time of these publications, various authors drew on their expertise in the languages of remote communities around the world to either generally support (*e.g.* Atran 1999, Brown 1986, Hays 1979, Hunn 1975, Scott 2000) or challenge (*e.g.* Bulmer 1974, Dwyer 2005, Ellen 2008, Sillitoe 1995) Berlin’s claims.

In recent years, however, interest in the question of universals in ethnobiological classification has waned considerably (Zent 2009, Ludwig 2018). Moreover, later ethnobiological papers that deal with naming and classification often make little or no attempt to either situate the names in a broader linguistic context (to demonstrate, for instance, community norms regarding the correct usage of the names; but see Amith (2020), Sellers (2015) and Wierzbicka (1992) for multiple illuminating examples) or to provide linguistic evidence to support claims made about the purported ‘rank’ of a particular term (see below for an explanation of ‘rank’). Even when this vital supporting information is presented, there is often a general reluctance to overtly criticise Berlin’s model, in spite of the data presented showing clear deviations from the predicted patterns. In her detailed and insightful description of Thai plant naming patterns, for instance, Singnoi (2011) makes use of contextualised linguistic data to present numerous

violations of key predictions made by Berlin's model. Unfortunately, the author never explicitly states how the data relate to the model, although Berlin's works are cited as a primary motivation for her research. A related phenomenon, where authors conclude that their data "fit[s] well in Berlin's general principles and corroborates the existence of universals in folk classification systems" (Hiepko 2006, p.447), in spite of one or more key predictions being violated, can also frequently be encountered in the literature (e.g. Valenzuela 2000, Mandaville 2004). There may also be bias present in what is reported in the literature and what is not. Ludwig (2018:421) sums up the issue as follows: "One of the most persistent problems of convergence metaphysics is that it seems to neglect or even marginalize classifications that do not converge on modern biology". An unfortunate consequence of these oversights is that Berlin's predictions are often presented in fieldwork guides aimed at both linguists (McClatchey 2011) and non-linguists (Martin 2004) as though they were wholly uncontroversial, instead of as hypotheses to be tested against new data.

Here, we present linguistic data from a number of south-east Asian languages in order to test two strong claims made by Berlin *et al.* (1973) and Berlin (1992) regarding the naming of plants and animals cross-linguistically. Some of the features of his theory that pertain to the current paper are as follows:

1. Taxa are grouped inclusively into a hierarchic (taxonomic) structure.
2. Taxa are spread out over six ranks or levels, whose content is comparable to the ranks of western biological classification. The six folk ranks are Kingdom [also called the Unique Beginner], Life Form, Intermediate, Generic, Specific and Varietal.
3. There are two kinds of names – primary and secondary. Primary names can be simple (*dog*) or complex (*forget-me-not*), while secondary names are complex (*white oak*), and contain the name of an immediately higher taxon (*oak*). Complex primary names can be productive (*catfish*)¹, or unproductive (*silverfish*). Secondary names form part of a contrast set (*white oak* and *red oak*).
4. Generic, Life Form and Intermediate taxa are labelled by primary names, while subgeneric taxa (with notable exceptions) are labelled by secondary names.
5. A subgeneric taxon is given a primary name if it is either the prototype of the genus, or of major cultural importance.

The existence of classificatory 'ranks' is key to Berlin's conception of folk classification; these ranks are supposed to be comparable across languages, and additionally, members of a particular rank within a language are also supposed to be comparable to each other (*i.e.* form part of a set). In this paper, we primarily investigate the naming patterns of two ranks, namely Life Form and Generic. The

¹ The distinction between productive primary names and secondary names is particularly relevant for this paper, and will be investigated further in Sections 2.1.5 and 3. Briefly, we assert that the majority of (Generic) plant and animal names discussed in this paper are actually secondary names, which violate Berlin's predictions.

Life Form rank often contains the categories such as ‘tree’, ‘vine’ and ‘herb’ for ethnobotanical classifications, and ‘bird’, ‘fish’ and ‘bug/insect’ for ethnozoological ones. These are supposed to be few in number, and to include, within themselves, the vast majority of ethnotaxa that are labelled in a given language. Brown (1977a and b) has even argued that certain Life Form labels (such as ‘tree’) are near-cross-linguistic universals, but the claim remains contentious. Life Forms are labelled by primary names.

The Generic rank is said to contain the vast majority of the ethnotaxa that are recognised and labelled in a language. The Generic rank of a folk classification is meant to be the most salient to speakers of that language; Importantly, Generic taxa are labelled by primary names (*e.g.* ‘trout’, ‘crow’, ‘maple’). Berlin, along with other adherents of his model (*e.g.* Brown 1985), insist that even though it is possible to say ‘oak tree’ or ‘hickory tree’ in some contexts and/or dialects, the ‘tree’ morpheme is ultimately optional. Therefore, ‘hickory’ fulfils the criterion of being a primary name, because the naming principle “applies to the *habitually necessary* components of the labels by which ethnobiological taxa are named” (Berlin 1992:28; italics added). Finally, Specific and Varietal taxa are labelled by secondary names, *i.e.* “linguistically complex expressions, one of whose constituents indicates a category superordinate to the form in question” (*ibid.*:28).

Readers with expertise in south-east Asian languages may, at this stage, find it hard to reconcile their own data and experiences with some of the “universals” described above, especially in relation to the restrictions on the nomenclature of Generic labels. This is not surprising, as mainland south-east Asian (MSEA) languages were largely left out of early efforts (in the 1970s-1990s) to determine cross-linguistic commonalities in ethnobiological classification. A lack of comprehensive ethnobiological studies on the languages of this region at the time may have been responsible for the omission. Indeed, the only languages from Asia, that are mentioned in the works of Berlin and his contemporaries², have a definite geographical bias: Hanunoo (Philippines), Tawbuid (Philippines), Bontoc (Philippines), Tasaday (Philippines), Casiguran Dumagat (Philippines) and Hill Pandaram (southern India). Looking further afield, we also find a handful of other languages of the wider Asia-Pacific region: Ndumba (Papua New Guinea), West Futuna (Futuna, New Caledonia), Kalam (Papua New Guinea) and Bellonese (Solomon Islands). Detailed studies on ethnobiological classification have also been carried out for the languages Nage (Flores Island, Indonesia) (*e.g.* Forth 2003, 2016), Eastern Sumbanese (Sumba Island, Indonesia) (Forth 2000)

² Brown (1977a and b) does use data from languages such as Thai, Vietnamese, Jarai and Tibetan, but solely in the form of dictionary entries, and only to determine if certain Life Form terms exist in those languages. In a later monograph, Brown (1984) also consults ethnobiological reports for numerous languages including Lao (Vidal 1963), but once again, only to identify words that correspond to ‘tree’, ‘vine’, and so on. See Footnote 9 about potential issues relating to the use of dictionaries or word lists for research on ethnobiological nomenclature.

and Nuaulu (Seram Island, Indonesia) (e.g. Ellen 2008), which have revealed varying levels of correspondence with the patterns predicted by Berlin.

Conspicuous by their absence from the above list, however, are MSEA languages. Recently, there have been attempts to investigate the broad morphosyntactic and semantic features of plant and animal names in a handful of east-Asian and MSEA languages (Matisoff 2011, Kurabe 2020), but with no explicit reference to Berlin's model. The inclusion of such languages is a welcome addition to the field of ethnoclassification, but the strong "universals" posited by Berlin (1992) remain to be tested for the vast majority of MSEA languages. Chamberlain's (1977) work on the Tai languages is the only comprehensive study of mainland southeast Asian faunal nomenclature. Chamberlain demonstrated that the Tai zoological system does not reflect a hierarchy, but rather "follows an anthropocentric structuring in terms of an organism's relative distance from humans, usually according to form, but also in terms of domestication and mythical properties" (1997:46). This leads him to the conclusion that universal taxonomic categories have utility as labels, but for speakers of Tai languages what is more salient is for example, the presence or lack of homologous arms and legs. In Tai languages, the inclusion of Unique Beginner and Life Form taxa in animal names (see Section 2.4 for more details) clearly defines some distinctions between domestic and wild (Chamberlain 1992). This principle of anthroproximity has been explored in the case of Sida (Tibeto-Burman) animal terminology, where it is articulated in terms of a domestic-wild continuum indicated with indexical and iconic depiction through reduplication and sound mutation (Badenoch 2021).

In this paper, we investigate two key points of Berlin's (1992) nomenclatural universals, namely that Generic taxa are primary names, and that, by definition, the superordinate label (the Life Form name 'tree', 'bird', 'fish', etc.) should not feature in the names of Generic taxa. Our approach to the question in this paper is to first re-examine the overt marking systems and lexical signification in the Generic taxon labels of the languages of MSEA, to demonstrate larger tendencies in the region that can help guide more in-depth work in specific languages. Already, there are convincing counter-examples to this prediction in the published ethnobotanical literature, but these seem to have been overlooked. In his documentation of plant names in three languages of Laos, the botanist Jules Vidal (1959:563) makes some interesting observations on the structure of the ethnotaxon labels, and explicitly mentions the ways in which his data presentation scheme differs from normal speech patterns:

Dans un but de simplification [...] je n'ai pas mentionné les appellatifs usuels qui précèdent le nom (nha, dok, mai, etc.) même si parfois ils en sont inséparables.

Ainsi, Eriocaulon cinereum s'appelle en laotien 'nha²kă tay ou encore 'nha² dok 'khao, c'est-à-dire respectivement herbe lapin et herbe fleur blanche. Je n'ai conservé que kă tay et 'khao.

For the sake of simplification [...] I have not mentioned the usual labels which precede the name (*nha* [grass], *dok* [flower], *mai* [wood/tree], etc.) even though they are sometimes inseparable from it.

Thus, *Eriocaulon cinereum* is called 'nha²kă tay or 'nha² dok 'khao in Lao, meaning rabbit grass and white flower grass respectively. I have only retained kă tay and 'khao.

Vidal notes correctly that the Life Form labels 'herb', 'tree' and 'vine' often appear as an obligatory, first part of the name of many plants in Lao. These Life Form labels occupy the same morphosyntactic slot as several other botanical "class terms" such as 'flower', '(leafy) vegetable', 'fruit' and 'root/tuber/bulb' (along with possibly 'bird', 'fish', 'snake' 'insect' in the zoological domain), and are usually analysed as such in descriptions of MSEA languages (e.g. Jenny and Htun 2016, Matisoff 2011, Singnoi 2011).

In a recent study on Lisu (Tibeto-Burman) Sellers (2015) found that of 350 recorded plant names, around 67% contain a class term suffix of some kind – these include the lexemes for 'tree', 'vine', 'bush/clump' and 'weed/herb' (see also Bradley (2006)). A small number of names have optional class terms, but ultimately there are 200 plant names (57% of the total) in which the class term (i.e. Life Form label) is obligatory. Intriguingly, there seems to be a degree of instability built into the Lisu ethnobotanical nomenclature, as individual plant ethnotaxa may be placed in different Life Form categories, depending on the immediate context.

Labelled botanical groupings such as '(leafy) vegetable', 'root/tuber/bulb', 'flower' and 'fruit' have often been considered to be part of edible-plant-only "special purpose" or "utilitarian" classification schemes (based on a few features or attributes), that can exist in parallel with the "general purpose" hierarchies (based on many features) proposed by Berlin (Berlin *et al.* 1973, Berlin 1992:185-190; but see Atran (1985), Hunn (1982), Randall and Hunn (1984) for alternative viewpoints). Sellers (2005) notes that for Lisu, the 'vegetable, edible' class was only volunteered by consultants during a plant sorting task, and not during plant collection, when the more standard Life Form categories were used. An investigation of the status of utilitarian "class terms" and the potential implications of these and general purpose Life Form labels being grammatically equivalent in many MSEA languages would be interesting, but is beyond the scope of the present study.

In the following, we discuss in some detail the nomenclature of plants, birds, fish and terrestrial invertebrates in four MSEA languages that we are more familiar with. These are Burmese (Tibeto-Burman, henceforth TB) and Thanau (Austroasiatic, henceforth AA) for author AS, and Bit (AA) and Lao (Kra-Dai) for author NB. Extensive studies on the ethnobiological classification systems of each of these languages could be carried out in isolation, and indeed, this would be a valuable addition to not only the field of ethnobiology in general, but also to our knowledge of these important, but understudied languages. Such studies will undoubtedly uncover numerous interesting historical and contact-based ethnobiological phenomena: in Burmese, for example, the Unique Beginner *təreiʔs^han* ‘animal’ is a Pali loan; as it is a Romance loan in English. Our intention here is not to provide a comprehensive analysis of the above four languages, but only to highlight the relevant data and morphosyntactic and semantic patterns required to test Berlin’s claims. Note that the two AA languages included are respectively in contact with the two national languages discussed, namely Burmese and Lao. Plants, birds and fish were chosen because (1) they are most likely to show violations of Berlin’s predictions (as opposed to mammals, for instance), and (2) because they are likely to be included in field linguists’ dictionaries (as opposed to reptiles and amphibians). We are mindful of Chamberlain’s (1977) assertion that humans’ conceptualisation of the semantic domains of plants and animals is very different, and that scholars of ethnobiological classifications should be careful not to lump them together within a single schema. While we discuss the naming of both plants and animals in this study, it should be noted that we focus only on nomenclature here, and do not make any claims regarding classification or categorisation at this stage.

In this paper, we also survey a number of other languages, using our own field notes and/or published fieldwork-based dictionaries³ and ethnobiological reports, in order to provide a rough overview of nomenclatural patterns in the languages of the region. In doing so, we hope to determine (1) whether there are areal patterns in ethnobiological nomenclature in MSEA languages, and (2) to what extent Berlin’s predictions regarding the relation between Life Form and Generic labels apply to these languages.

³ As mentioned in Footnote 7, data in the form of dictionary entries should be used with caution. One simple way to reduce the risk of misunderstanding is to carry out Google searches for phrasal plant and animal names, to verify their acceptability among native speakers. For instance, a search for the Vietnamese *cây đa* ‘banyan tree’ returned over 1.8 million hits, confirming that *cây* ‘tree’ is an integral part of the name. Similarly, a search for the Thai ต้นสน *tôn sǎn* ‘pine tree’ returned nearly 2.5 million hits. This could understandably not be carried out for many of the smaller languages mentioned in this paper.

2. LANGUAGE DATA

2.1 *Burmese*

Burmese (Tibeto-Burman, >30 million L1 speakers) shows considerable variation from Berlin’s scheme in the nomenclature of living organisms. Even language internally, speakers use very different strategies in the naming of organisms included within the Life Form taxa *ηà* ‘fish’, *ti? pin⁴* ‘tree’ and *ηε?* ‘bird’. Burmese has two main ways of modifying nouns that are relevant to ethnotaxonomy: head nouns can be modified by a V or N that appears after the head noun (*e.g.* ‘bulldog’ below), or by a N that appears *before* the head noun. In the following examples incorporating the head noun *k^hwè* ‘dog’, the resulting lexemes can be interpreted as the names of either ‘kinds of’ dogs or ‘animals closely related to’ dogs (1). These include:

(1) Burmese ‘dog’ words

a. <i>k^hwè bəlù</i>	dog ogre	‘bulldog’
b. <i>k^hwè á</i>	dog be.mute	‘jackal’
c. <i>mje gwè</i>	ground dog	‘fox’
d. <i>tò k^hwè</i>	forest dog	‘wild dog’, ‘village dog’

The above examples suggest that the slot following the head noun is reserved for intrinsic attributes of the noun (*e.g.* head-N or head-V = ‘head that has the attribute N/V’), whereas the N-head construction is reserved for ‘head that is associated with N’ (in the case of the fox, this is an allusion to its subterranean dens). However, Kurabe (2020) has identified numerous other patterns among Burmese zootaxon names, and it becomes difficult to apply the above semantic generalisation across all known patterns. More fine-grained analysis is required in this respect, to determine the motivation for the two different syntactic patterns in ethnotaxon names. To complicate matters further, Burmese prefers the head-initial strategy in the case of fish names, but the head-final strategy for plant names (a pattern also noted by Jenny and Htun 2016). Thus, even within a single language, there is clear variation in the formation of Generic level taxon names. The following discussion illustrates the point that the vast majority of these Generic level names are not primary names, but are instead obligatory secondary names. Note that contemporary descriptions of Burmese morphosyntax (*e.g.* Jenny and Htun 2016, Kurabe 2020) tend to conflate various levels (ranks) of Berlin’s hierarchy: accordingly, *k^hwè bəlù* ‘bulldog’ probably of Specific rank (with *k^hwè* ‘dog’ as the Generic), and *ηə-dʒìn* ‘mrigal carp’ probably a Generic (with *ηà* ‘fish’ as the Life Form), are treated as comparable lexemes. In the following discussion, we focus on ethnotaxon labels of the second type.

⁴ In the Burmese transcriptions, syllables ending in ‘n’ represent nasal vowels.

2.1.1 Fish

In the vast majority of Burmese fish names, the head slot is occupied by the morpheme *ηà* ‘fish’, which compound-initially is realised as *ηə-*. The following slot is occupied by nouns or verbs (or VPs, as in the case of ‘loach’ below) that can describe the physical appearance of the fish, the characteristics of its meat, or various behavioural or ecological features of the species (2).

(2) Burmese fish names

a. <i>ηə-ɔ̀zìn</i>	[fish-?] ‘mrigal carp’	*ɔ̀zìn
b. <i>ηə-ján</i>	[fish-?] ‘ <i>Channa micropeltes</i> ’	*ján
c. <i>ηə-mjiʔ-tʃín</i>	[fish-river-?] ‘ <i>Labeo rohita</i> ’	*mjiʔ-tʃín
d. <i>ηə-tʃəlɛ-tʰò</i>	[fish-sand-poke] ‘loach’	*tʃəlɛ-tʰò

The *ηə-* morpheme is an integral part of all these names, and cannot be omitted under any circumstances⁵.

Precise quantitative data for Burmese are not available, but Judson’s (1893) Burmese-English Dictionary lists 102 fish names beginning with *ηə-*. The Myanmar Language Commission’s (1993) Myanmar-English Dictionary lists 55. As it is difficult to determine from these sources how many fish names lack the ‘fish’ morpheme, a proxy analysis of the closely related languages of two fishing communities of Myanmar – Intha and Rakhine – was carried out. A total of 29 (freshwater) fish names were documented for Intha, which is spoken in several villages on the shores of Inle Lake; of these, close to 90% were binomials, incorporating the *ηə-* ‘fish’ morpheme (Si and Kyawphyo 2023). Similarly in Rakhine, spoken on the western coast of Myanmar, 74% of 131 recorded (marine and estuarine) fish names contained *ηə-* ‘fish’ (Table 1). It is therefore very likely that the vast majority of Burmese fish names will follow a similar pattern.

Interestingly, the names of a small number of aquatic creatures follow the head-final template, where the terminal slot is occupied by *ηà*. These organisms contrast with the fish named *ηə-x*, in that the former are not true fish, but a mixed group of organisms, including *pjedzì ηà* ‘squid’ and *welá ηà* ‘whale’. The higher-level taxa *jedzo ηà* ‘freshwater fish’ and *pinle ηà* ‘marine fish’, as well as ornamental fish such as *fwe ηà* ‘goldfish’, also follow this pattern. In Intha, the only ethnotaxon labels that show this pattern is *fwe ηà* ‘gold fish’, which is the name given to an introduced, farmed species of carp (*Cyprinus rubrofuscus*), and *tçau? ηà* ‘rock fish’, the name for the introduced tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). Interestingly, an alternative local name for the latter fish is *səlápíyá*, a clear loan of the English name; its “foreign” status is marked by the fact that it is one of the only primary names in the local fish lexicon, one which does not combine with

⁵ Note, however, that the omission of *ηə-* may occasionally be permitted in closely related languages or dialects. Thus, while *ηə-fín* is the Burmese name for ‘eel’, the Rakhine name is simply *fín*. This is an exceptional case, as the vast majority of Rakhine fish names also have an initial *ηə-*.

either $\eta\partial$ - or $\eta\grave{a}$. In Rakhine, the name $t\grave{c}au\eta\grave{a}$ ‘rock fish’ is used to label various colourful reef fish (such as those from the families Pomacentridae (butterfly fish), Lutjanidae (snappers) and Pomacanthidae (marine angelfish)), which are usually only targeted by specialist fishermen, and/or not consumed locally. The X $\eta\grave{a}$ pattern therefore invokes a sense of atypicality or aberration, reminiscent of the ‘fox’ example discussed above.

A small number of Burmese fish names appear to be direct loans from the neighbouring Mon language (Jenny 2015), and include commercially important ethnotaxa such as $ka\eta\ k\grave{a}di\eta$, $ka\eta\ t\grave{a}baun$ ‘sea bass (*Lates calcarifer*)’, $ka\eta\ kujan$ ‘Indian threadfin, four-finger threadfin (*Leptomelanosoma indicum*, *Eleutheronema tetradactylum*)’, $ka\eta\ t\grave{a}mj\eta$ ‘bronze croaker (*Protonibea diacanthus*)’ and $ka\eta\ t\grave{a}b\grave{o}$ ‘tank goby (*Glossogobius giuris*)’. All these names retain the original Mon head $ka\eta$ for ‘fish’, but note that in Rakhine, the name for the sea bass is $\eta\partial$ - $t\grave{a}dai\eta$, with the Mon $ka\eta$ being replaced by a Burmese-like $\eta\partial$.

2.1.2 Plants

The naming of plants in Burmese also systematically violates Berlin’s predictions, but in subtly different ways. First, the lexeme ∂pin ‘plant’ could be considered a Unique Beginner, as it encompasses practically all organisms that might be placed in the biological Kingdom Plantae *sensu stricto*⁶. The lexemes $t\grave{i}\eta\ pin$ ‘tree’ and $nwe\ bin$ ‘vine’, on the other hand, whose translations suggest that they should be considered Life Forms, are analysable as ‘wood plant’ and ‘vine plant’ respectively, and therefore not primary names. This in itself is a violation of Berlin’s prediction that Life Form terms are primary names cross-linguistically.

Plant taxa that might be considered to be of Generic rank are also secondary names⁷, as shown by the following examples. Unlike the fish names, which commonly incorporate the Life Form $\eta\partial$ -, plant names obligatorily include the Unique Beginner term pin as their second element, regardless of the Life Form category they belong to (3). Burmese speakers will say that a $b\grave{a}dau\eta\ pin$ (*Pterocarpus macrocarpus* plant) is a kind of $t\grave{i}\eta\ pin$ ‘tree’, and group it with other trees.

⁶ Some exceptions might include small, morphologically undifferentiated organisms, such as mosses and algae.

⁷ The morpheme pin is often omitted in dictionaries of Burmese, such as the online SEALang Library Burmese Dictionary (<http://sealang.net/burmese/dictionary.htm>), but this is more a lexicographic convention than a reflection of normal speech practices. There is some indication that the second part of a name is more readily omitted than the first in elicited word lists, as the same dictionary includes the word-initial $\eta\partial$ - in fish names.

(3) Burmese plant names

a. oùn bin	coconut plant	‘coconut palm’
b. bə̀dau? pin	padauk plant	‘padauk tree’
c. n̄ə̀you? pin	chilli plant	‘chilli plant’
d. zə̀bəlín-bin	lemongrass plant	‘lemongrass’
e. bù bin	gourd plant	‘bottle gourd vine’
f. wà bin	bamboo plant	‘bamboo’

Note that example 4b, which patterns along the lines of the English ‘There is an elm growing in my garden’, is ungrammatical. This violates Berlin’s prediction that Generic terms will largely be composed of primary lexemes.

(4)

a.	n̄á	tʃan	dè	ma	bə̀dau?	pin	də-bin
	1SG.OBL	garden	in	at	padauk	plant	one-plant

shí də
be NFUT

‘There is a padauk tree in my garden.’

- b. *n̄á tʃan də ma **bə̀dau?** də-bin shí də
*‘There is a padauk in my garden.’

It is necessary to distinguish edible staples from ornamental or ‘wild’/‘forest’ plants, when talking about naming patterns. This is because the names of a handful of plants that may broadly be construed as ‘vegetables’ or ‘fruits’ behave differently from the names of the ethnotaxa discussed so far. In the following two examples (5), the ethnotaxon labels obligatorily include the part of the plant that is consumed, namely the leaf and the fruit:

(5) Plant names that mention ‘leaf’ and ‘fruit’

a. myìn khwa ywə? pin	horse hoof leaf plant	‘Asiatic pennywort’
b. pàn ðì bin	flower fruit plant	‘apple tree’

There is a small number of ornamental plant names that include the morpheme ‘flower’, whereas in the word for ‘tomato plant’, the ‘fruit’ morpheme may be optional for some speakers (6):

(6) Plant names that mention ‘flower’ and optionally, ‘fruit’

a. sɛʔku bən bin	paper flower plant	‘bougainvillea’
b. khə̀yàn jin (ðì)bin	aubergine sour (fruit)plant	‘tomato plant’

The above naming pattern, which incorporates a plant part morpheme, as well as the Unique Beginner label ‘plant’, is rare in Burmese, but is far more widespread in some of the other languages discussed below (see Sections 2.2.1,

2.3.1; also A sho Chin, Lainong Naga, Palaung and Vietnamese in Table 1; see Section 2.4.2 for the Unique Beginner ‘animal’).

The status of ‘Specifics’ *sensu* Berlin (1992, in the context of cultivated plants) is also interesting. A number of different kinds of mango, banana and chilli are well-known in Myanmar (7), and include the following:

(7) Varieties of some cultivated plants

mango:

- | | |
|------------------------------|------------------------------|
| a. s ^h ein təloun | ‘diamond one.fruit’ |
| b. yin gwè | ‘chest split’ |
| c. màndələ | ‘PLACE.NAME’ |
| d. má chíʔsú | ‘Miss FEMALE.NAME’ |
| e. bədəmjà ɲəmauʔ | ‘diamond ?’ |
| f. mjá təuʔ | ‘emerald stone’ |
| g. ʃwe hinda | ‘golden shelduck’ |
| h. ʔoun loun dədaun | ‘three fruit.COUNT one.yard’ |

banana:

- | | |
|--------------------------|------------------|
| a. p ^h i dʒàn | ‘? coarse’ |
| b. ʔi ɲwè | ‘fruit fragrant’ |
| c. yəkhain | ‘PLACE.NAME’ |
| d. s ^h in zwe | ‘elephant tusk’ |
| e. ʃwe ɲəpjə | ‘golden banana’ |
| f. ɲwe ɲəpjə | ‘silver banana’ |
| g. ɲəpjə dʒin | ‘banana sour’ |
| h. kəyin ʔi | ‘Karen fruit’ |
| i. nanʔəpú | ‘?’ |

chilli:

- | | |
|----------------|---------------------|
| a. kələ-ʔau | ‘Indian-shout’ |
| b. mò ɲjə | ‘sky gaze’ |
| c. təwè dəbaun | ‘buffalo one.thigh’ |
| d. təuʔ sein | ‘rock green (jade)’ |
| e. aʔ tan | ‘needle stick’ |

The above names, when used as shown, refer to the edible plant product, *i.e.*, the mango, banana or chilli fruit. When the referent is the plant, it is acceptable, in some contexts, for the Generic or Unique Beginner label morphemes to be omitted (8-10):

- | | | | | | | |
|-----|---|-----|--------------------|-----------|---------|---------|
| (8) | èda | gá | s ^h ein | təloun | (ʔəjəʔ) | (pin) |
| | that | TOP | diamond | one.fruit | (mango) | (plant) |
| | ‘That is a s ^h eĩ təloũ (mango tree).’ [e.g. while pointing at the tree] | | | | | |

(9) tu gá p^hidzàn (bin) dwe əmjà.dzì
 3SG TOP SPECIFIC (plant) PL many
 saiʔ t^hà dɛ
 grow keep NFUT
 ‘He is growing many p^hidzàn [banana] (plants).’

(10) nǎ yɛ’ mò mǎjɔ (bin) lè tɛ tɰwà byi
 1SG POSS sky gaze plant little die go PRF
 ‘My poor mo mǎjɔ (chilli plant) has died.’

The subgenerics (*i.e.* levels included within a Generic category) mentioned in the above examples appear to be labelled by primary names. Berlin (1992) does mention that certain subgenerics can be labelled by primary names, as long as they are prototypical for the contrast set (*i.e.* the category labelled by the immediately preceding Generic) or they are of major cultural importance (see point 7 of his nomenclatural principles, above). The above-mentioned types of mango, banana and chilli are no doubt culturally important, although it is debatable if they can all be said to be “prototypical” for their respective classes. Still, we conclude that the Burmese data on plant subgenerics lend partial support to the generalisation made in Berlin (1992)⁸.

2.1.3 Birds

Bird names in Burmese follow another pattern altogether, and constitute the only group of names in the current dataset that can be said to largely comprise of primary lexemes at the Generic level. Unlike fish and plant names, the morpheme representing the Life Form taxon *ŋɛʔ* ‘bird’ is not included in the names of the majority of bird species (11):

- (11) Birds with primary names
- | | |
|---------------------|-----------|
| a. bɛ̀ | ‘duck’ |
| b. daùn | ‘peacock’ |
| c. tɛigàn | ‘crow’ |
| d. k ^h o | ‘pigeon’ |
| e. byain | ‘stork’ |
| f. lɛdá | ‘vulture’ |
| g. zìgwɛʔ | ‘owls’ |

In the closely-related Danu dialect spoken in Aungban, Pindaya and surrounding villages, we find that between 26% and 38% of bird names contain the *ŋɛʔ* ‘bird’ morpheme (Table 1). A similar figure is obtained for the more

⁸ Note that Berlin himself cites work by Terence Hays and Paul Taylor that provides examples of subgenerics that are *not* culturally significant, and are nevertheless labelled by primary names (Berlin 1992, p. 118). Berlin concedes that the claim made in point 5 of his nomenclatural principles (see Introduction) is therefore not a cross-linguistic universal.

divergent Intha; here, around 23% of bird names incorporate the ‘bird’ morpheme. Examples of this pattern include $\eta\epsilon^? t\omega$ ‘drongo’ (lit. ‘bird royal’), $\underline{t}\epsilon\grave{i}n \eta\epsilon^?$ ‘falcon’ and $\eta\epsilon^? py\grave{i}n$ ‘nightjar’ (lit. ‘bird lazy’). Unlike Burmese fish names, there seems to be no clear rationale that governs the placement of the head $\eta\epsilon^?$ word-initially or word-finally, and in the Danu dataset, both appear with an equal frequency (roughly 10 items each). In both types of names, the morpheme(s) accompanying $\eta\epsilon^?$ can refer to salient attributes of the bird in question: $\eta\epsilon^? ni d\grave{z}\grave{i}$ (bird red big) ‘Greater Coucal’; $t\epsilon w\epsilon^ \grave{t}\epsilon a\grave{u}n \eta\epsilon^?$ (cow herd bird) ‘Jungle Myna, Common Hill Myna’. The attribute in head-final bird names commonly incorporates a transitive verb phrase, as in $t\epsilon w\epsilon^ \grave{t}\epsilon a\grave{u}n$ (cow herd (V)) above, or in the examples $\underline{t}\grave{i}^? \tau a\grave{u}^? \eta\epsilon^?$ (wood peck bird) ‘woodpecker’ and $\eta\grave{a} s\grave{a} \eta\epsilon^?$ (fish eat bird) ‘herons’. These names fall under the very productive [[N-V]-N] category of compound zoonyms described by Kurabe (2020). In contrast, transitive verb phrases never appear in head-initial bird names in our data (although Kurabe (2020) does provide a single counterexample of a Specific-level bird name: $z\grave{a}j\epsilon^? t\grave{f}\grave{i} s\grave{a}$ (myna shit eat) ‘Pied Myna’. This and other potential semantic or morphosyntactic correlates of $\eta\epsilon^?$ placement warrant further investigation.

2.1.4. *Terrestrial invertebrates*

The Burmese general term for insect or bug is $p\grave{o} gaun$ (silk animal), and refers prototypically to the silkworm. Both elements of the name, i.e. $p\grave{o}$ ‘silk’⁹ and $kaun$ ‘animal’ appear as the second element of a number of terrestrial invertebrates, as in $w\grave{a} p\grave{o}$ ‘bamboo grub’, $p\grave{o} ha^?$ ‘cockroach’ and $\underline{t}\grave{a}n gaun$ ‘tapeworm’. $P\grave{o} gaun$ in actual usage probably refers primarily to noxious insects or insect pests, rather than to more benign creatures such as dragonflies ($b\grave{a}z\grave{i}n$) or butterflies ($lei^?pja$). Regardless of whether $p\grave{o} gaun$ is analysed as a Life Form, Intermediate or Generic label, it incorporates the Unique Beginner $kaun$ ‘animal’, and is therefore a secondary name. Moreover, the Generics within this category (if $p\grave{o} gaun$ is a Life Form) are also labelled by secondary names, with $p\grave{o}$ appearing in first or second position as with the bird and fish names, and $kaun$ usually occurring in the second position, similar to pin ‘plant’.

2.1.5 *A note on primary and secondary names*

It is important, at this point, to consider the distinction between the productive primary names and secondary names (Berlin 1992, Berlin *et al.* 1973) alluded to in the Introduction. In both the above publications, the nomenclatural rules allow Generic ethnotaxa to be labelled by complex (multi-word) names called productive primary names. Examples include *catfish*, *bluebird* and *bullfrog* (Berlin 1992:28), and these ethnotaxa belong to the superordinate categories *fish*,

⁹ The word $p\grave{o}$ (with the sense ‘insect’ or bug’ as in the compound $p\grave{o} gaun$) seems to have undergone a semantic extension to also mean ‘pathogen’ as in $j\grave{o}ga p\grave{o}$ ‘disease germ(s)’ or $kow\grave{i}^? p\grave{o}$ ‘COVID virus’.

bird and *frog* respectively. Researchers who encounter numerous such examples in their target language often state that their data do not violate Berlin's prescription regarding the labelling of Generics by primary labels, as labels of the type *x-tree* and *y-fish* are indeed productive primary, and not secondary, names (e.g. Hunn 2008, Sellers 2015). Should the Burmese fish and plant names described above as secondary lexemes therefore be analysed as productive primary names as well, thereby negating the problem of violating Berlin's model? Berlin's thoughts on the two types of names are instructive here. In Berlin *et al.* (1973:217):

...secondary lexemes differ from productive primary expressions in that the former occur only in contrast sets, all of whose members are labelled by secondary lexemes which share the same superordinate constituent... Productive primary lexemes such as *planetree*, *tuliptree*, and *leadtree*, however, occur as members of contrast sets of which some members are labelled by expressions such as *maple*, *walnut*, *elm*

Note that the English examples of productive primary lexemes cited in publications such as Berlin *et al.* (1973) and Berlin (1992) – *planetree*, *tuliptree*, *leadtree*, *pipevine*, *crabgrass*, *catfish*, *bluebird*, *bullfrog* – have in common the feature that the non-Life-Form morpheme in these names (*tulip*, *pipe*, *crab* etc.) have real-world referents other than the plant or animal that the complete, two-part names allude to. Most of the Burmese examples presented above pattern differently, and in the case of the tree *bədau? pin* (*Pterocarpus macrocarpus* plant), the abbreviated name *bədau?* still refers to the tree in question. Such abbreviations, however, occur only in very specific speech contexts, such as reciting a list of plants.

A key criterion for identifying secondary lexemes is that “all” members of the relevant contrast set also be secondary lexemes. It is hard to say with certainty if there are any instances in our data of Generic-level contrast sets, of which “all” members are secondary lexemes; this is because these sets are so large, and often contain hundreds of items. However, there are numerous cases where the overwhelming tendency is for Generics to be labelled by two-part names, one of which is obligatorily the superordinate Life Form or Unique Beginner label. Taking the Burmese fish names as an example, the vast majority share the same superordinate constituent *ŋə-* ‘fish’, and are in a large contrast set of similar names. In each of these names, the initial *ŋə-* or the final *ŋà* are strictly necessary. Burmese plant names are also two-part names – possibly without exception – as are many of the Generic categories in some of the languages described below. Moreover, as noted in the Introduction, Berlin (1992:128) also states that names like *hickory* and *hickory tree* are interchangeable, and that “the presence of the constituent *tree* is not necessary”. Berlin's model therefore implicitly requires the majority of Generic labels to be to be simple primary names like *hickory*. There also appears to be no clear linguistic distinction between productive primary

names and secondary names, which is probably why linguists have tended to conflate the two in their analyses.

To sum up our understanding of Berlin's definitions: 1) labels like *hickory tree*, *oak tree* are simple primary names because *hickory*, *oak* are acceptable alternatives, 2) labels like *planetree*, *tuliptree* are complex primary names because *tree* cannot be omitted, and these plants occur in a contrast set with numerous exemplars (presumably a majority of the members of the set) of the type *hickory*, *oak*, and 3) labels like *red oak*, *cork oak* are secondary names because of the superordinate category label *oak* that is common to all members of the contrast set. Burmese fish and plant names cannot be characterised adequately by the first two criteria, as the 'plant' and 'fish' morphemes are obligatory and widespread. We therefore treat two-part names of the type *ηə-dʒin* (fish mrigal.carp) and *wà bin* (bamboo plant) as secondary names in this and subsequent analyses in this paper.

2.2 Thanau

The AA isolate Thanau is spoken by roughly 5,000 people living in a handful of villages between the town of Aungban and Inle Lake in Shan State. While the majority of people in the state speak various dialects of Shan, the Thanau communities themselves are largely surrounded by villages that are home to Pa'O (TB) speakers (Si 2014). Moreover, they come into regular contact with Danu (TB), Intha (TB) and Palaung (AA) speakers over the course of trips to local markets¹⁰. Not many fish are to be found on traditional Thanau lands; hence, this section focuses on plant, bird and invertebrate names.

2.2.1 Plants

The botanical Unique Beginner in Thanau (*sou?* 'plant') is incorporated into the botanical Life Form label 'tree' just like in Burmese: *sou?* *t^hē* (lit. 'wood plant'). There appears to be no label corresponding to 'vine', while grasses can be labelled by the umbrella term *ḥō*. Thanau Generic plant names, like Burmese, incorporate superordinate labels to a large degree; in fact, 65% of recorded plant names (70 out of 108)¹¹ are at least bipartite (*i.e.* secondary names), and have *sou?* 'plant' as the head of the noun phrase (*e.g.* *sou?* *kədu* 'pine tree', *sou?* *umu* 'gourd vine'). Tripartite plant names are also very common (12), and usually make reference to the part of the plant that is utilised. In most cases, these are the wood *t^hē*, fruits *ple* and flowers *pō*.

¹⁰ There is a moving market that is held in the towns of Aungban, Kalaw, Nyaungshwe, Taunggyi and Heho in a five-day cycle.

¹¹ These plant names were collected as part of a general language documentation project, and no special effort was made, at the time, to determine if it would be appropriate to incorporate *sou?* into the plant names which were volunteered as bare forms (*i.e.* without *sou?*). It is highly likely that this is the case, and if so, the percentage of bipartite Generic plant names in Thanau would be much higher.

(12) Tripartite Thanau plant names

- | | | |
|---|-------------------------------|---------------------------|
| a. souʔ t ^h ē k ^h ruu | plant wood k ^h ruu | ‘type of woody tree’ |
| b. souʔ ple kûn | plant fruit betel | ‘betelnut/areca nut tree’ |
| c. souʔ pô ŋgāj | plant flower ŋgāj | ‘frangipani’ |

Some variation was noted, in our dataset, in the use of *souʔ* ‘plant’, *ple* ‘fruit’ and *pô* ‘flower’. In a handful of cases, the presence or absence of the latter two terms helps to distinguish between different ethnotaxa, as in the case of *souʔ ple kûn* (plant fruit betelnut) ‘betelnut tree, *Areca catechu* and *souʔ kûn* (plant betel) ‘*Piper betle* vine’. These two terms are strongly lexicalised, and therefore invariant. In most other cases, however, the variation appears to be context-dependent, or a result of individual speaker preference. With regard to the former, *souʔ* ‘plant’ is often dropped during repeated naming tasks or when a list of plants is being recited. Inter-individual variation is also evident here, however, as some speakers still provide the complete ethnotaxon name in such speech contexts, whereas others choose to drop *souʔ*, *ple* and *pô* in these situations. Speakers may also disagree about the degree to which these morphemes are lexicalised in the ethnotaxon labels. Given that the Thanau word for ‘jackfruit’ is *ple palã*, with the initial *ple* meaning ‘fruit’, some speakers will say that the jackfruit tree is called *souʔ ple palã* (plant fruit jackfruit), *i.e.*, using the maximally elaborated name. Some speakers, however, insist that the correct name would be *souʔ palã*, without the ‘fruit’ morpheme. This is reminiscent of the Burmese pattern discussed above, and it is possible that the latter, shorter variant is mostly used by younger Thanau speakers, who have had more contact with Burmese and Danu. This possibility needs to be investigated systematically.

In Thanau, as in Burmese, the names of some cultivated vegetable crops display regular deviations from the norm. Plants such as cabbage and snow pea can be referred to without the need for superordinate morphemes (13), such as *souʔ* ‘plant’. The following examples illustrate this point:

(13)

- | | | | | | |
|----|---------------------|------|-----|--------|---------------------|
| a. | kõk ^h ĩẽ | naʔ | nəʔ | sam.pũ | tumwān.bəloũ |
| | field | this | TOP | grow | cabbage |
| | ḅōʔ | ŋkô | | | |
| | many | lots | | | |

‘There are many cabbages growing in this field.’

- b. kōk^h.iē naoʔ.le sam.pū **baj.hàm** ɓōʔ ŋkô
 field another grow snow.pea many lots
 ‘There are many snow pea (plants) growing in another field.’

2.2.2 *Birds, fish and invertebrates*

Among Thanau bird names, around 48% (of a documented total of 60) were found to incorporate the Life Form lexeme *san* ‘bird’. Interestingly, the remainder were also dominated by bipartite names, but here the head noun was *majʔ* ‘?mother’ (Si 2016). Fish names follow a similar pattern to Burmese, with the majority of (if not all) fish ethnotaxon labels incorporating the lexeme *p^hjəŋ* ‘fish’. Finally, some terrestrial invertebrate names also include the superordinate taxon label *pli* ‘bug/insect’. It is curious that some insect names also have *majʔ* as the head noun, reminiscent of many bird names (e.g. *majʔ t^hin* ‘Asian honeybee’). Note that a similar phenomenon can be observed in Palaung (Table 1). It is possible that such names are only used for social insects that are exploited by humans for their larvae or honey. Social insects such as termites, which are not consumed, or solitary insects, such as mosquitoes and flies, have monomorphemic names (*k^h.a*, *təf.iāt* and *.wi* respectively).

2.3 *Bit*

Bit is spoken by about 2,400 people living in the mountainous areas along the borders of Laos, Vietnam and China. It is an AA language¹², and its speakers now make their livelihoods in upland agriculture, hunting, gathering, and fishing. Although many Bit villages are increasingly integrated into the socioeconomic life of towns, speakers of the language generally maintain intimate daily relationships with forest ecosystems.

2.3.1 *Plants*

The most general form occurring in tree Generic names is *tap*, meaning ‘trunk’ or ‘stalk’. However, it is not a straightforward matter to equate *tap* with the Unique Beginner ‘plant’. *Tap* is also found in the Life Form term *tap cɔuəŋ* ‘tree’. Tree names include discrete etymological names and descriptive names, but it should be noted that *cɔuəŋ* is never found in tree names. Among the trees with descriptive names, there is a small number of trees that include the word *tap* ‘trunk’ in the name (see (17) below), comprising 10% of the total number of Bit tree data (n=71). An example of a descriptive name that does not require *tap* is *cvŋ rwaal* (bitter exceedingly), which is recognized as the name of a specific tree. When discussing tree names, Bit speakers say that tree names can be said with or without *tap*, but including the term indicates that one is speaking of a definite tree of reference. In this sense, *tap* functions more as a noun classifier. People agree

¹² Bit data employs NB’s orthographic convention in which long vowels are written as double (/aa/), /y/ is [j] and the final /-s/ denotes [-j^h].

that although all trees can take *tap*, it is only required for that small number of trees. This is confirmed by this passage (14) from a folktale setting the stage at a large ficus (*diə*) tree:

- (14) snmaan ləʔ **diə** kdiinj
 long.ago exist ficus large
 kndai kal kɔɔ bah klɔk
 whoever chop then NEG fall.over
 “In the old days there was a large ficus, it wouldn’t fall no matter who chopped at it.

or a request to a child get a *naa waay* ‘Siam weed plant’ (15)

- (15) waʔ dɔk **naa waay** kɔɔy ʔεε meʔ
 go take Siam weed.pl bring give mother
 “go get a Siam weed plant (*Eupatorium odoratum*) and bring it to your mom”

and the general observation about *rsaan*, a type of bamboo (16) used for construction:

- (16) kheet həə **rsaan** ʔanrik nɔk yoʔ
 area that bamboo much very EMPH
 There is quite a lot of construction bamboo in that area.

The plants that do obligatorily take *tap* tend to be woody trees (16). Some examples include:

- (17) Bit woody tree names
 a. tap baʔ krɔm sɲɔ lɪi tree sour *krɔm* rice(sp.) ‘*Baccaurea motleyana*’
 b. tap paay sdɔ tree bean wind ‘*Cassia fistula*’
 c. tap may khwaan tree wood(T) *khwaan*(T) ‘*Azadirachta indica*’

Apart from *tap* ‘tree’, some other category labels that resemble Berlin’s Life Forms include *crmi* ‘vine’, *rik* ‘small herbaceous plant (including grasses)’ and *bat* ‘leafy plant’ (18). As with *tap* ‘tree’, the head morpheme *crmi* only appears obligatorily in a handful of instances. For example, *rmlaam* ‘type of creeper’ is the name of a vine, but some descriptive names may prefer the use of the term *crmi* *smpɔɔy* (vine magical.concoction), while others do not, such as *trbuəŋ kluəʔ* ‘feeder *kluəʔ* (bird)’. The categories *bat* ‘leafy plant’, *rik* ‘grass’ and *tih* ‘mushroom’ require the term as part of the name, with associated descriptive material. Of 16 mushroom names, all require *tih* and are semantically transparent. Interestingly, poisonous mushrooms are not named, but referred to generally as

tih kmbool ‘mushrooms poisoning’ because it is believed that the absence of names for dangerous mushrooms lessens the chance of confusion and mistaken ingestion.

(18) Bit plant names incorporating various Life Form labels

crmii ‘vine’:

- a. *crmii smpiət* - the parasitic vine *Cuscuta* sp.
- b. *crmii smpɔɔy* - the edible *Senegalia pennata* (formerly *Acacia pennata*)

rik ‘small herb/grass’

- c. *rik mnʔoh* - poss. the sensitive plant *Mimosa pudica*
- d. *rik mah taan* - Caesar weed (*Urena lobata*)

bat ‘leafy plant’

- e. *bat nɔɔr* - type of deciduous shrub (*Rhamnus nepalensis*)
- f. *bat crʔiiy* - edible river fern (*Diplazium esculentum*)

In addition, Bit names for many plants that bear edible fruits incorporate the lexeme ‘fruit’ into the plant name, as in Thanau. For instance, the wild bittergourd (*Mormordica charantia*) fruit is *plɛɛ pʰak hay*, where the head lexeme *plɛɛ* means ‘fruit’. The corresponding plant name would then be *crmii plɛɛ pʰak hay* (vine fruit *pʰak hay*). Trees known by their fruit or flower do not require *tap*. For example, the hairy fig (*Ficus hirta*) is named after the fruit *baʔ boʔ clek* (sour.fruit breast pig), but one may say *tap baʔ boʔ clek* (tree sour.fruit breast pig) when the speaker wants to refer to the standing tree. Similarly, *Mussaenda parvata* is *tap baar doldaal* (tree flower butterfly), and is called after the flower with similar referential context.

2.3.2 Birds

The Life Form ‘bird’ in Bit is *ceem*, and this form is used in around 40% of Generic bird names. The structure of bird names differs according to their etymology, comprising three broad categories: “old” AA forms, Life Form plus descriptor forms and Life Form plus mimetic forms. Speakers of Bit have been in close contact with speakers of Tai-Lao languages, that have a Life Form ‘bird’ *nok* that is an obligatory part of most bird names. Elicitation of Bit bird names shows some interference from this linguistic contact, and there is a trend for younger speakers to use the Life Form *ceem*, even though elders explain that this is ‘not correct’. For example, ‘Golden Pheasant’ is often named *ceem-tlir*, but older people claim that this is a ‘Lao’ way of saying the ‘correct’ name, which is merely *tlir*. Note that the figure of 40%, mentioned above, is based on the responses recorded from one older speaker (aged >40 years).

Many birds are known by discrete, monomorphemic etyma: *rec* ‘sparrow’, *kɾɿɔl* ‘bulbul’, *truəŋ* ‘hornbill’, *klaan* ‘hawk’, *trkuu* ‘dove’, *liəʔ* ‘parrot’ and

rmpvvl ‘Spotted Dove’, to name a few. These tend to have solid AA etymologies. As mentioned above, around 40% of bird names is composed of the Life Form head, followed by an attribute. The attribute can be descriptive, as in the case of *ceem baar lɣaa* (bird flower sesame) ‘Small Minivet’ and *ceem traak ɣvvc* (bird buffalo to.moan (of buffalo)) ‘Streak-eared Bulbul’, or mimetic, as in: *ceem ciac* ‘Slaty-backed Forktail’, *ceem cruum* ‘shrike’, and *ceem kdee* ‘weaverbird’. In the latter group, all attributes reference the call of the bird in question.

2.3.3 Fish and other creatures

Bit fish names are almost entirely primary names. The general word ‘fish’ *mɔuə* is a lexical innovation motivated by avoidance language in Bit fishing culture (Badenoch 2020)¹³. However, this common word for fish *mɔuə* is not used in any fish names; it would perhaps be more accurate to say that *mɔuə* cannot appear in fish names because of the taboo. The expected AA term **kaa* is found in only a few names, such as *kaa dvvɣ* (a type of small fish with a long, pointed mouth), and the meaning is no longer recognized by speakers as a general word for fish. It is not clear if the currently named fish previously had the head **kaa* that was dropped, but the syntax of some suggests this might be the case. Bit speakers fish in upland rivers and streams, which limits the fish they know to relatively small species. Unfortunately, precise scientific identification of the fish ethnotaxa has not been carried out. However, *blɔɔɣ* (river loach) *slaap* (small fish with barbs on back), *koom* (small meat-eating fish), and *trliiy* (small fish) are all etymologically ‘old’ Generic fish names. Elders are adamant that while all of these are *mɔuə* ‘fish’, they have their ‘own names’, none of which involve **kaa*. Fish named thus make up approximately 70% of the total named fish. The remaining 30 percent consists of descriptive names, while a small number of fish names includes the head *kaa*. In contrast to bird names, the descriptive group does not include a ‘fish’ element. The old term *kaa* is known in just three names. Interestingly, speakers of Bit understand *kaa* to be from Khmu, another Austroasiatic language that most Bit people speak. An example of a fish name with the *kaa* Life-form word include *kaa ɔvvc* (fish red).

Descriptive names without a head (that makes an indication to ‘fish’) are common: *crɔaap luəɣ* (opening.mouth.wide stone), refers to a fish that sticks to the underside of stones in shallow rivers, while *cldəap bvs* (bottom rice.steamer) and *sntaa sɣvɔ* (tongue rice.plant) probably make reference to the shape of the fishes in question.

Names for snakes follow suit, with the superordinate term *mar* ‘snake’ appearing in all names: *mar sɣmɛɣ* (snake star) ‘golden tree snake’, *mar pɔnim*

¹³ A similar example is that of the python. Bit snake names also incorporate the Life Form term *mar* (see below for details). The python is a culturally important snake for the Bit, and is known commonly as *mar ɔuun*, although in the Tai-Lao cultural area, this snake is usually is not considered part of the Life Form ‘snake’. Bit Elders agree that the snake is more correctly called *ɔuun*, but *mar ɔuun* has become the accepted name.

(snake termite.hill) ‘cobra’ and *mar plək snaat* (snake bullet) ‘krait’. The findings for Bit are supported by data from Khmu (see Table 1), a related AA language with which speakers of Bit have been in contact for generations. In Khmu, only 25% of fish names include the ‘fish’ element *kaʔ* with a descriptive attribute, while 13% of bird names share the same pattern, and incorporate *ceem*. All 19 Khmu snake names include *mar* along with an attribute that is semantically transparent.

Bit has no general word for ‘insect’. There are, however, numerous invertebrates or insects are named in Bit, such as *kuək* ‘worm’, *tykεε* ‘tick’, *təs* ‘grasshopper’ and *ʔvvy* ‘hornet’. Some insects show evidence of mimetic or expressive word formation: *lelaap* ‘flying termite’, *yol-yal* ‘cicada sp.’, *sooŋ-saaŋ* ‘dragonfly’, *ŋaaŋ-ŋooŋ* ‘gnat sp.’, *doldaal* ‘butterfly’, *kurnaar* ‘millipede sp.’, *leh-seh* ‘long-leg katydid’ and *ninuur* ‘cicada sp.’

2.4 Lao

Lao (Kra-Dai) is spoken by around 30 million people in Laos and Thailand. Ethnobiological classification in the Tai languages are some of the best understood in Southeast Asia, thanks to three decades of research by Jim Chamberlain. The Tai languages (of which Lao is one) are a diverse but coherent group of languages spoken across the region. These languages are important for an areal perspective because they have had huge influence on the AA and TB languages spoken in close proximity. Bilingualism – primarily among the non-Tai populations – has led to structural and lexical convergence in all areas of language, including flora and fauna nomenclature. Thus, Tai systems of naming plants and animals are important in both the synchronic and diachronic senses.

2.4.1 Plants

Plant nomenclature in Lao shows a strong tendency towards inclusion of the Life Form term, as well. In the world of flora, Lao nomenclature marks *tôn* (*mây*) ‘plant, tree’, *khú:ə* ‘vine’, *phák* ‘leafy vegetable’, *ŋä:* ‘grass’ (equivalent to *nha*² of Vidal (1959)). With the exception of *tôn* (which also means ‘origin’), flora nomenclature resembles the [Life Form + Generic] forms of faunal names (see below). The most common form is of the pattern *tôn sāk* ‘teak tree’, *tôn phá:w* ‘coconut tree’ and *tôn káthín* ‘type of acacia tree’. The bound relationship of this marker to the general is confirmed in (19a).

(19)

- | | | | | | | |
|----|-------------------------|-----|-----|------------|------------|--------|
| a. | yā: | pay | tát | tôn | sāk | khö:y! |
| | don’t | go | cut | tree | teak | 1SG |
| | Don’t cut my teak tree! | | | | | |

b. *yā: pay tát sāk khò:y

where (19b) is not accepted.

Trees that are known for their fruit often contain the word *mà:k* ‘fruit’ as well: *tôn mà:k mūə:ŋ* (tree fruit mango), *tôn mà:k kêə:ŋ* (tree fruit orange) and *tôn mà:k khă:m* (tree fruit tamarind). Several fruit trees that are also used for their wood or trunk can omit the *mà:k* element, such as ‘mango tree’ *tôn mūə:ŋ* or *tôn mà:k mūəŋ* and ‘banana tree’ *tôn kêə:y* or *tôn mà:k kêə:y*, but these forms are few in number.

Common reference to trees is complicated by the existence of another marker *mây* ‘wood’, which can replace *tôn* in cases where trees are utilized for their wood. So, in addition to *tôn sāk* ‘teak’, one will also hear reference to *mây sāk* ‘teak wood’ (as a standing tree as well as the timber) and *tôn mây sāk*. The difference between *tôn sāk* and *mây sāk* as references to a standing tree are explained by (20) and (21).

(20) óoo thě:w nīi **tôn** **sāk** khú: vāa lă:y thé:
oh area this tree teak seems.so many very
‘Oh! There are so many teak trees in this area!’

In (20) *ton* indicates that the individual trees are recognizable and could feasibly be counted, yet:

(21) óoo thě:w nīi **mây** **sāk** khú: vāa lă:y thê:
oh area this wood teak seems.so many very
‘Oh! There are so many teak trees in this area!’

where *mây* implies that the speaker is observing a population of trees forming an area of forest (21). As an aside, such an area may also be called *pā: sāk* ‘teak forest’. Note, however, the root (*hà:k*) of a teak tree is *hà:k tôn sāk* or *hà:k mây sāk*, but **hà:k sāk* is not allowed.

The other ethnobotanical Life Form terms are obligatory (22) in the names of non-woody plants:

(22) Lao plant names incorporating various Life Form labels

khú:ə ‘vine’:

a. khú:ə bâ: ‘type of vine *Entada rheedei*’

b. khú:ə tót mǎ: (vine-fart-dog) ‘type of vine’

phák ‘leafy vegetable’:

c. phák sí: ‘parsley’

d. phák ʔi: lə:t ‘wild betel’

ɲà: ‘grass’

e. ɲà: khá: ‘cogon grass’

f. ɲà: câw sũ: ‘love grass’

The form *tôn* may also be used with these plant names, but only with the Life Form marker and Generic; for example, *tôn mǎ:k phét* (tree fruit chilli) ‘chili pepper plant’, and not **tôn phét*. This indicates that the name of the plant requires marking with *mǎ:k* ‘fruit’. A similar requirement obtains for *phák* ‘leafy vegetable’, as in *tôn phák kǎ:t* (tree leafy vegetable lettuce) ‘lettuce plant’, and not **tôn kǎ:t*. Plant names in these categories demonstrate both lexical names and descriptive names. Similar patterns are observed by Singnoi (2011) for Thai plant names. Chamberlain (1992) has pointed out that many plants named are relatively recent introductions into the landscapes in which Lao speakers live, which is conducive to the basic word formation pattern of Life Form plus descriptive name.

2.4.2 *Animals*

Chamberlain’s work on Tai language fauna terms (1977) proposed a framework in which the Unique Beginner proto-Tai **tua/*dua* ‘body, animal’ (giving rise to modern Lao *tō:* ‘animal’) envelops a basic bifurcation of naming strategies in taxonomy. One group is composed of terms with [Unique Beginner + Generic], including domestic animals, mammals, auspicious birds, python, lizards, turtles softshell turtles, amphibians, swamp eels, arthropods, crustacea and annelids. For example, we find *tō: kwâ:ŋ* ‘deer’, *tō: mǔ:* ‘pig’ and *tō: kǎy* ‘chicken’. In most cases, *tō:* is not mandatory, but preferred. Sometimes, however, the inclusion of *tō:* is obligatory, as in *tō: pét* ‘domestic duck’ and *tō: nōk pét* ‘wild duck’ (Chamberlain 1992).

In the second group, we find names marked with mandatory Life Form elements (23). The names of the members of this category have the form [Life Form + Generic], and this pattern holds for birds (**nrok* DS), snakes (**ŋwaa* A), fish (**plaa* A), arthropods (**mleŋ* A) and molluscs (**hwii* A). Following are some examples:

(23) Lao animal names incorporating various Life Form labels

nōk ‘bird’:

- | | |
|--------------------|-------------|
| a. <i>nōk cə:k</i> | ‘sparrow’ |
| b. <i>nōk thá:</i> | ‘partridge’ |
| c. <i>nōk khâw</i> | ‘owl’ |

ηú: ‘snake’:

- | | |
|-------------------|--------------------------|
| d. <i>ηú: hāw</i> | ‘cobra’ |
| e. <i>ηú: sǎ:</i> | ‘radiated rat-snake’ |
| f. <i>ηú: dìn</i> | ‘iridescent earth snake’ |

pà: ‘fish’:

- | | |
|---------------------|---------------------------------|
| g. <i>pà: khó:</i> | ‘freshwater scaleless fish’ |
| h. <i>pà dùk</i> | ‘silurus fish’ |
| i. <i>pà: khá:η</i> | ‘large-mouthed freshwater fish’ |

All of the above can take the Unique Beginner *tō:*; for example *tō: ηú:* ‘snake (general)’, *tō: ηú: hāw* ‘cobra’, *tō: nōk thá:* ‘partridge’ and *tō: pà: khá:η* ‘large-mouthed freshwater fish’. These patterns hold for *mé:η* ‘arthropods’ and *hǎ:y* ‘molluscs’ as well. Exceptions to this core Unique Beginner/Life Form pattern exist, but can be explained by the cultural semantics of these animals in the Lao worldview. For example, we find that *lǔə:m* ‘python’ is not typically marked as ‘snake’ and *kâ:* ‘crow’ is not usually marked as ‘bird’¹⁴. Both are instead marked with the Unique Beginner *tō:*.

It is interesting to note the division of insects into arthropods marked as Life Form *mé:η* and others marked with Unique Beginner *tō:*. Of the 43 items with Lao cognates listed in Chamberlain’s (1997) comparison of insect names, 29 are *tō:* and 14 are *mé:η*. This list also provides important insight into the variation of naming conventions within the Tai family. For example, while ‘gadfly, horsefly’ is *mé:η lǔə:k* in Lao, it is *tō: lǔə:k* in the closely related Tai Vat language. Divergence is also evident at a deeper timescale across the main branches of Tai.

¹⁴ Spiritual beliefs about the python’s position within Tai cosmology have resulted in historical traditions of avoidance in many related languages, while the crow is inauspicious within Tai beliefs about birds as messengers from the other world (Chamberlain p.c.)

Language name (Source)	Plant names	Bird names	Fish names	Invertebrate names
Tibeto-Burman (N=7)				
Asho Chin (AS field notes, native speaker consultant from Paukkhaung, Myanmar, recorded in Yangon)	Yes joũ ‘plant’ ? ‘tree’ wáj joũ ‘mango tree’ həmə? joũ ‘chilli plant’ tə ?ó joũ ‘gourd vine’	No/?Rare (3%, 34) phəjə ‘bird’ ʈáj phəjə ‘?buttonquail’ sí só ‘Red-vented Bulbul’ singəli ‘Green Bee-eater’	Yes ŋá ‘fish’ ŋəlédoú ‘striped snakehead’ ŋək^hú ‘Philippine catfish’ ŋəsəlú ‘small freshwater fish’	Rare pú gəú ‘bug/insect’ jó pú ‘bamboo grub’ dǎ? dəlǎ pú ‘ <i>Moringa</i> grub’ háj? ‘mosquito’ k ^h wé ‘bee’ mlǎ ‘ant’
Burmese (AS field notes, native speaker consultants, Yangon)	Yes pin ‘plant’ ʈɪ? pin ‘tree, wood plant’ ʈəjə? pin ‘mango tree’ ŋəjou? pin ‘chilli plant’ bù bin ‘gourd vine’	Sometimes (26%, 50 to 38%, 42) ^a ŋɛ? ‘bird’ ŋɛ? tə ‘Bronzed Drongo’ ʈɪ?tau? ŋɛ? ‘woodpeckers’ zì gwɛ? ‘large owls’ bjain ‘crane, stork, heron’	Yes (74%, 131 to 90%, 29) ^b ŋà ‘fish’ ŋəmjin ‘silond catfish’ ŋəp^hɛ ‘bronze featherback’ ŋətəlau? ‘hilsa’	Sometimes pò gəun ‘bug/insect’ (lit. silkworm) jin gaun ‘fly’ ti gaun ‘earthworm’ wà pò ‘bamboo grub’ pjà ‘honeybee’
Lahu (Matisoff 2006)	Sometimes (55%, 56) cè , ə-cè ‘plant’ šɪ? - cè , šɪ? -bɪ ‘tree’ kə - cè ‘Malayan spurge’ nyòw - cè ‘ <i>Bombax malabaricum</i> ’ á-mò? = qō = te ‘gourd vine’	Sometimes (33%, 36) ŋâ? ‘bird’ a-tɛ -tɛ = ŋâ? ‘lapwing’ ŋâ? = nɔ -ma ‘Gold-fronted Leafbird’ cí-ca-kwɪ ‘Black Drongo’	Yes (90%, 33) ŋâ , pá ~ pa ‘fish’ pa -ká? ‘ <i>Tricopsis vittata</i> ’ hɔ - ŋâ (= pá) ‘loach’	Rare pú ~ p̄u ~ p̄u ~ p̄u ‘insect, bug, vermin, ?silkworm’ p̄u -tì ‘earthworm’ p̄u -thu ‘inchworm’ pê ‘bee, wasp, hornet’ pə? -mā ‘caterpillar’ pí -ma (= qō) ‘housefly’

Lainong Naga (AS field notes, native speaker consultant from Lahe, Myanmar)	Yes gàj ‘plant’ jò ‘rope, vine’ ? ‘tree’ loũ kwī gāj ‘mango tree’ tsin gāj ‘pine tree’ sōŋ tçu gāj ‘chilli plant’ kàmki jò ‘pumpkin vine’	Sometimes (52%, 62) vuì ‘bird’ vuìpuì ‘partridge’ ameĩvuìsəu ‘swifts/swallows’ sāfī ‘Bronzed Drongo’	Yes niú sɛu ‘fish’ niú phwè ‘small, flat-bodied silver fish’ niú twè ‘?snakehead sp.’ nā ljá ‘fish sp.’	Rare vòŋ ‘bug/insect’ njìm vòŋ ‘insect parasite of sesame’ kàfɔ vòŋ ‘bean parasite’ næ ‘honeybee’ tsè pou ‘cockroach’
Pa-O (AS field notes, native speaker consultant from Aungban, Myanmar)	Yes tɛĩ mù ‘tree (wood plant)’ tɔwi (mù) ‘vine’ təkʰɔ? mù ‘mango tree’ tçen mù ‘chilli plant’ sì se? mù ‘gourd vine’ bè tɔwi (mù) ‘bean vine’	Yes (68%, 47) wé ‘bird’ wé kuu ‘pigeon’ wé tʰi ‘cormorant’ sək è ‘crow’	Yes tʰɛ? ‘fish’ [most fish names borrowed from Burmese, also contain ɲə- ‘fish’ as the second element] tʰɛ? ɲədʒin ‘mrigal carp’ tʰɛ? ɲəján lòn ɔwá ‘snakehead variety’	No tɛ? ‘bug/insect’ pitʰu ‘fly’ phrum ‘blowfly’ təwət ‘honeybee’
Sgaw Karen (AS field notes, native speaker consultants from Taungoo, recorded in Yangon)	Yes tɛ⁴ tʰu⁴ ‘tree (wood plant)’ kəme⁵ tʰu⁴ ‘tree sp. (<i>Syzygium</i> sp.)’ xə⁶ tʰu⁴ ‘coconut palm’ pəhi⁴ tʰu⁴ ‘teak tree’ kʰlu¹ tʰu⁴ ‘banyan tree’ wa⁴ tʰu⁴ ‘bamboo’	Yes/?Sometimes (62%, 21) tʰo⁴ ‘bird’ tʰo⁴ wi⁶ ‘quail’ tʰo⁴ pʰwi⁶ pʰo⁶ ‘sparrow’ tʰo⁴ ble⁴ blə⁴ ‘swallows’ (tʰo⁴) do⁶ kə?o⁶ ‘owls’ so³ wa⁴ xa³ ‘crow’ lə⁵ kəta² ‘vulture’	Yes ɲa⁴ ‘fish’ ɲa⁴ yu² ‘carp’ ɲa⁴ kədɔ⁴ ‘snakehead’ ɲa⁴ la² ‘bronze featherback’ ɲa⁴ tu⁴ ‘climbing perch’	No da¹ ya² ‘mosquito, insect’ kəne⁶ ‘bee’ pəʔu³ ‘termite’ tə?bi⁶ la⁶ ‘fly’ g

Ethnobiological nomenclature in southeast Asia

Sida (Badenoch 2021)	Sometimes suteú ‘tree’ te ^h ng àteú ‘chestnut sp.’ ng ‘banana plant’ th ^h iteú ‘type of hardwood tree’ hlapó ‘type of long sectioned bamboo’ mapi ‘chili plant’	No khijà ‘bird’ lopjò ‘bulbul, large sp.’ ò ‘hornbill’ teh ^y wa ànalà ‘White-cheeked Laughing Thrush’	Sometimes (54%, 13) ngòt ^r ‘fish’ txn^r ‘red catfish’ pjepò ‘minnow’ (<i>Bangana</i> sp.) ngòng ‘black shark minnow’ (<i>Labeo chrysophekadion</i>) ngòtx-lòjò ‘stone loach’ (<i>Barbatula barbatula</i>)	No [no general term] pìteà ‘cicada’ útehé ‘centipede’ kèpa ‘water leech’ k ^h uhé ‘flea’ teèkòlò ‘mantis’
Austroasiatic (N=10)				
Bit (NB field notes, native speaker consultants from Luang Namtha; Badenoch 2020)	No (13%, 84) tap c ^ʔ uəŋ ‘tree’ crmii ‘vine’ (tap) c ^ʔ rii ‘banyan’ tmaay ‘hurricane palm’ tap diə ‘fig (<i>Ficus fistulosa</i>)’ crmii smp ^{iət} ‘parasitic vine (<i>Cuscuta</i> sp.)’ crmii smp ^{ooy} ‘edible climber (<i>Senegalia pennata</i>)’ m ^ʔ iət ‘chili plant’ b ^{ooy} ‘loofah plant’	Sometimes (36%, 61) ceem ‘bird’ krjəl ‘bulbul’ trkuu ‘turtle dove’ tlir ‘Silver Pheasant’ ceem ciəc ‘White-crowned Forktail’ ceem brkwak- kwaak ‘White- breasted Waterhen’	No m^ʔuə ‘fish’ bləŋ ‘loach’ slaap ‘eel’ (<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>) trliiy ‘fish sp.’ crleem ʔuəy ‘fish sp.’	No [no general term for insects] kuək ‘caterpillar’ clteep ‘dog flea’ ninuur ‘cicada sp.’ rooŋ ‘termite’ saante? ‘cockroach’ sb ^{iət} ‘cliff hornet’

Kacho' (NB field notes, native speaker consultants from Rattanakiri, Cambodia)	Yes sɔəm lɔːŋ 'tree' sɔəm kǎnuu 'tree sp.' sɔəm lɔŋ tniŋ ' <i>Pterocarpus macrocarpus</i> '	Sometimes ndaup 'bird' (cɛɛm 'bird' in names) cǎwɔny 'drongo' ŋgajŋ '(large) hornbill' (sp.) pɪ̀ək 'large-tailed nightjar' cɛɛm ndaup 'emerald dove' cɛɛm poot 'barbet' cɛɛm bubuu? 'greater coucal'	Yes kaa 'fish' kaa mɔɔm 'sucking loach' kaa ŋgɛɛŋ 'catfish' kaa ŋat 'small fish sp.'	No tyɔɔc 'red ant' wee yaaw 'small cicada sp.' tʃiŋ tʃɛɛp 'millipede' yaʔ paum 'dragonfly' hǎdɪaŋ 'caterpillar'
Khmer (SEAlang 2007a)	Sometimes daəm cʰǎə 'tree' daəm svaay 'mango tree' cʰǎə plǎəŋ 'kind of small tree with corrosive sap' snao 'small swamp plant (<i>Aeschynomena aspera</i>)' kantrook 'woody vine sp. (<i>Limonia monophylla</i>)'	No baksəy 'bird' pəpic 'Indian White-eye' (<i>Zosterops palpebrosus siamensis</i>) caap 'sparrows' krasaa 'heron' (<i>Ardea</i> sp.)	Yes trəy 'fish' trəy kanlaŋ 'fish sp.' trəy crakaɛŋ 'fish sp.' (<i>Barbus siaja</i>)	No sat lʔət 'general term of insects, arachnids and other small insect-like animals' kandoop 'grasshopper' kʔaep 'centipede' ruy 'house fly' kandiə 'termite'
Khmu (Svantesson et al. 2014)	No túut sʔɔŋ 'tree' hmpóɔr 'tamarind' lwà ' <i>Ficus</i> sp.' kmrəʔ lmpò ' <i>Millettia lasiopetala</i> ' pltàap ' <i>Leucopogon</i> sp.' plòŋ cáŋ 'bitter rattan' lmtaar 'vine sp. with edible fruit'	Sometimes síim 'bird' síim lwàaŋ 'green bee eater' síim òm 'forktail enicurus' còŋ 'grackle' kíaŋkíaŋ 'hornbill'	Yes ká 'fish' ká lá 'type of fish' ('leaf fish') ká cáat 'type of fish'	No iŋkíi 'bamboo eating) beetle' hóos 'grasshopper' kláap 'brown winged termite' híŋ kàaŋ 'house louse' clél 'cicada (<i>Cryptotympana pustulata</i>)'

Mon (SEAlang 2009a)	Yes chu 'tree' (cf. nəm) choa 'herb' chu 'kroik 'silk cotton tree' chu 'kla' 'teak tree' choa hloij 'sensitive plant' choa hləm 'kind of trefoil'	Sometimes həcem 'bird' həcem kəmaiŋ ³ aŋ 'Pied Hornbill' həcem kəloij ² 'Common Myna' həcem həkrò' 'Green Bee- Eater' hədaik 'crow'	Yes ka kətəm 'butterfish' ka səlak 'hilsa' ka krəŋ ' <i>Cirrhina</i> <i>mrigala</i> '	Sometimes kəma 'bug/insect' kəma hətè' 'cockroach' kəma sɔ' 'weevil' kəma əkrəaŋ 'locust'
Palaung (AS field notes, native speaker consultants from Taungni, Myanmar)	Yes həj 'plant' ? 'tree' həj dərək 'banyan tree' həj bləj mo 'mango tree' həj məp ^h rit 'chilli plant' həj bləj kəpəɔ 'gourd vine'	Sometimes (27%, 41) məsī 'bird', also mə '?mother' məsī gəbrə 'White-throated Fantail' məsī krə 'nightjar sp.' mə læē 'parrots' mə prē 'Eurasian Hoopoe'	Yes məgu? 'fish' məgu? ŋədʒĩ ' <i>Cirrhina</i> <i>mrigala</i> ' məgu? ŋək ^h u 'Philippine catfish'	Unclear According to three wordlists presented in Rattanaipitak (2009), many invertebrate names begin with <i>ma-</i> , but this is probably the same prefix (etymology unknown) that occurs in many bird, fish, reptile, amphibian and mammal names, <i>e.g. ma phian</i> 'cockroach', <i>ma</i> <i>buax</i> 'barking deer', <i>ma rux</i> 'turtle'
Phong Laan (NB field notes, native speaker consultants from Vang Vieng, Laos)	No lam sʔuŋ 'tree' (lam) laa 'banana tree' ksaa 'chestnut' dardəɔ ' <i>Oroxylum</i> <i>indicum</i> ' ʔarnaa 'type of long sectioned bamboo' pray 'chili plant'	Sometimes som 'bird' som gwaar swaan 'woodpecker' ʔii pləw 'type of bird' giʔgraaŋ 'kingfisher' kaʔkooh 'type of bird'	No kaa 'fish' trii 'river loach' [most fish names borrowed from Tai-Lao with paa 'fish'] paa k ^h iij 'type of small fish' paa məəm 'type of small fish'	No ʔii kol 'beetle, downward tusks' ʔii deel 'type of black ant' taʔkəh 'grasshopper, short tail' sdiij kiip 'beetle sp.'

Thanau (AS field notes, native speaker consultants from Taungbohla, Myanmar)	Yes (63%, 109) sou? t ^h ē ‘tree (plant wood)’ sou? (ple) pəlâ ‘jackfruit tree’ sou? mī t̃fê ‘chilli plant’ sou? u mū ‘gourd vine’	Sometimes (48%, 60) sən ‘bird’, měj? ‘?mother’ sən kɛtɛn ‘Hill Partridge’ sən tɕɛ ‘Large Hawk-Cuckoo’ měj? t̃t̃t̃ ‘Spotted Dove’ měj? ku pɛt ‘Coppersmith Barbet’	Yes p^hjəŋ ‘fish’ p^hjəŋ p ^h ɛj ‘ <i>Notopterus</i> <i>notopterus</i> ’ p^hjəŋ kərə? ‘striped snakehead’	Sometimes pli? ‘bug/ insect’, měj? ‘?social insect’ pli? kərə? ‘bamboo grub’ pli? sou? sei? ‘hairy caterpillar’ měj? oŋ ‘hornet?’ měj? t ^h ɛj t ^h ɛj ‘giant honeybee’
Vietnamese (SEAlang 2009b)	Yes cây ‘plant’ cây xoài ‘mango tree’ cây đa ‘banyan tree’ cây tre ‘bamboo plant’ cây ớt ‘chilli plant’ cây bí ngô ‘pumpkin vine’	Sometimes chim ‘bird’ chim sɛ ‘sparrow’ chim gô kiên ‘woodpecker’ chèo bèo ‘drongo’ bông lau đít đỏ ‘bulbul’	Yes cá ‘fish’ cá trắm ‘pike’ cá thồn bon ‘sole’ cá chạch ‘loach’ mực ‘squid’	Sometimes bọ ‘insect, worm, flea’ bọ đất ‘wood- louse’ bọ ngựa ‘praying mantis’ châu châu ‘grasshopper’ môi ‘termite’
Wa (Watkins 2013)	Sometimes (29%, ~480) khaox ‘tree’ khaox rung ‘banyan tree’ khaox gix ‘pine, <i>Pinus</i> <i>yunnanensis</i> ’ kat rhax ‘ <i>Acacia</i> sp.’ jhie: ‘fan palm’ (<i>Livistona</i> <i>chinensis</i>) peep ‘tree sp.’ (? <i>Artocarpus</i> <i>pithecogallus</i>)	Rare/?Sometimes (18%, 185) sim: ‘bird’ paog ‘Green- billed Malkoha’ braing ‘Purple- naped Sunbird’ eappid ‘Common Cuckoo’ sim: gawx khaox ‘woodpecker’	Yes (94%, 19) kax ‘fish’ kax heeik ‘catfish sp.’ kax plaok ‘redeye barb’ kax ting kaing ‘snakehead fish’ gawb mox ‘flat headed fish’	Rare/?Sometimes (19%, 176) kawng ‘insect’ viag ‘wriggling insect’ aing: ‘mud dauber wasp’ dee ‘aphid’ lu: liex ‘water beetle’ kawng taux ‘snout moth larva’ viag long: ‘woodworm’
Kra-Dai (N=3)				

Lao (NB field notes, native speaker consultants from Vientiane, Laos; SEAlang 2007b)	Yes tôn ‘tree’, kok ‘tree’ tôn (mây) ‘tree, plant’ tôn mã:k mūa:ŋ ‘mango tree’ kók nã:t ‘tree, bark used for tanning’ [see text for other Life Forms]	Yes nok ‘bird’ nok k ^h wak ‘bulbul’ nok k ^h ua: ‘pheasant’	Yes pà: ‘fish’ pà: síw ‘small carp’ pà: dúk ‘catfish’	Sometimes mé:ŋ mâj ‘insect’ mé:ŋ ván ‘house fly’ mε:ŋ sǝ:n ‘mole cricket’ mōt ‘ant’ bōŋ ‘caterpillar’ cī: ná:y ‘field cricket’
Shan (AS field notes, native speaker consultant from Aungban)	Yes toǎn³ mɛj⁵ ‘tree’ toǎn³ mɛj⁵ ŋon ‘banyan tree’ toǎn³ mək² moŋ ³ ‘mango tree’ toǎn³ mək² p ^h jet ⁵ ‘chilli plant’ toǎn³ mək² nem ⁵ t̥ə ³ ‘gourd vine’	Yes (86%, 28) ^c nok⁵ ‘bird’ nok⁵ sǝ ² ‘sparrow’ nok⁵ pǝ ³ ‘Asian Koel’ kɛj ² ‘chicken’	Yes pɛ¹ ‘fish’ pɛ¹ jɪn ³ ‘eel’ pɛ¹ ləm ² ‘striped snakehead’	Sometimes mjəŋ⁴ ‘insect’ mjəŋ⁴ mɔn ⁴ ‘fly’ mjəŋ⁴ sɛ ³ ‘dragonfly’ phuŋ ³ ‘honeybee’ jɔŋ ⁴ ‘mosquito’
Thai (SEAlang 2006)	Yes tôn (máay) ‘tree’ t^hǎw ‘vine’ p^hâut ‘?herb, ?plant’ tôn sǝn ‘pine tree’ tôn maak ‘areca palm’ máay dɛɛŋ, tôn dɛɛŋ ‘ironwood (<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i>)’ t^hǎw p ^h rík ^h ay ‘pepper vine’ p^hâut p ^h rík ‘chilli plant’	Yes nók ‘bird’ nók kra‘jàap ‘weaverbird’ nók naaŋ ‘èn ‘swallow’	Yes plaa ‘fish’ plaa mùk ‘squid’ plaa kòt ‘catfish’ plaa c ^h a‘nàak ‘sawfish’	Sometimes malɛɛŋ / mɛɛŋ ‘insect’ mɛɛŋ mum ‘spider’ mɛɛŋ pǝɔ ‘dragonfly’ mɛɛŋ daa ‘horseshoe crab’ ják.ka‘jàn , loŋŋ nay ‘cicada’ p ^h âŋ ‘bee’ yuy ‘mosquito’
Hmong-Mien (N=2)				

Kim Mun (NB field notes, native speaker consultants from Luang Namthta, Laos)		Sometimes nɔ ³³ ‘bird’ nɔ ³³ kələk ³¹ ‘hornbill’ nɔ ³³ bəkɔ ⁵³ ‘dove’ nɪn ³³ bjəw ⁵³ nɔ ³³ ‘kingfisher’ toŋ ³³ ŋeŋ ⁵⁵ ‘woodpecker’		Sometimes kjeŋ ⁵³ ‘insect’ kjeŋ ⁵³ na ⁵⁵ ‘spider’ kjeŋ ⁵³ ndjaj ⁵³ ‘pill millipede’ θəj ²² ‘flea’ mbjɛn ⁵³ ‘cockroach’ səblaw ³¹ ‘termite’
White Hmong (Heimbach 1969, native speaker consultant recorded in California by NB)	Yes ntoo ‘tree’ ntoo daj tawv ‘large tree with yellow wood below the bark’ ntoo txiv txhais ‘mango tree’	Sometimes noog ‘bird’ noog nu vaj ‘hornbill’ piv ‘sparrow’ nquab ‘pigeon’	Yes ntses ‘fish’ ntses dawb ‘type of white fish’ ntses los zeb ‘type of rock loach’ ntses noj quav ‘type of fish (fish eat shit)’	Sometimes kab ‘gen. term beetles, caterpillars’ kab nqos vias ‘locust’ (sp) kab laug sab ‘spider sp.’ kooj tshuab ‘locust’ (sp) tshauv ‘head lice’

Note: Orthographies used in the source texts have been retained. Numbers in parentheses indicate the % of secondary (productive, two-part) Generic names, followed by the total number of Generics recorded for that category (if available). ‘Yes’ denotes that the superordinate category label is incorporated in most (>60%) Generic names; ‘Sometimes’, 20%-60%; ‘Rare’, <20%; ‘No’, 0-2 tokens documented.

^a Figures from a list of Danu bird names; the two sets of figures indicate variation between speakers from two villages, ^b Figures from a list of Rakhine and Intha fish names, ^c Figures from a list of Tare Shan names

Table 1. Language-specific tendencies regarding the incorporation of a superordinate (Life Form or Unique Beginner, shown in bold) category label in Generic names.

2.5 Other languages

Table 1 presents some other languages, from four different language families of MSEA, for which lexical ethnobiological data are available. The data show that the use of secondary names for Generic labels is indeed an areal feature, as 13 languages (out of a total of 22) had a strong preference for incorporating Life Forms such as ‘tree’ or even the Unique Beginner ‘plant’ into their ethnobotanical Generic labels, while a further five languages (two TB and two AA) had a moderate preference to do so. Only three languages (all AA) had a preference for primary ethnobotanical Generic names. Variation in the choice of Life Form could be found at the language family level; thus, within Kra-dai, Shan utilises a combined ‘plant/tree’ superordinate label across all Life Forms, whereas Thai and Lao require a different label for each Life Form. Moreover, some of the data presented in Table 1 were obtained from dictionaries, which for the reasons mentioned above, may result in an underestimate of secondary names in these languages. In the language Khmu, for instance (Svantesson et al. 2014), fish and

bird names both incorporate Life Form labels, and it is surprising that plant names should not follow suit.

Secondary names were also strongly dominant in the ethnoichthyological lexicon for most languages (18 had a strong preference for secondary names), with only one (TB) showing a moderate preference, and two (both AA) preferring primary names. Bird names showed a very different pattern, with 14 languages displaying a weak to moderate preference for secondary names, and three languages (one TB and two AA) preferring primary names. Terrestrial invertebrates were the least likely biological domain to exhibit secondary names, with 13 languages showing a weak to moderate preference for secondary names, and eight (2 TB and 9 AA) preferring primary names. Overall, the patterns exhibited by plant names seemed to correlate well with that of fish names. This suggests that cross linguistically, terrestrial arthropods might be regarded as a category distinct from the other animal groupings investigated here.

The comparative data show historically solid etymologies of taxonomy within clusters of related languages yet demonstrate complicated semantic nuance. For example, the interplay between the ‘tree’ terms *tôn*, *mây* and *kók* in Southwestern Tai languages presents a difficult situation, even in discussion with speakers. The “rules” that obtain for these processes may be a subject of debate within the communities, as seen in the data for Thanau, Bit and Lao. Many of the smaller Austroasiatic languages surveyed have been in historically close contact with different Tai and/or TB groups (Bit with Lue/Tai Khaw, Khmu with Lue/Lao, Kacho’ with Lao, Phong Laan with Phuan/Tai Dam, Thanau with Pa’O and Shan, and Wa with Lue/Shan), with varying possibilities of contact-driven change often over periods of high mobility. Additionally, the prevalence of multilingualism among upland groups, facilitating complex socio-economic and cultural exchange networks, has had impacts on these systems that can be observed in action today. Other contact situations involving larger languages like Burmese, Mon, Karen and Thai signal the need to consider areal patterns of ethnobiological classification at multiple scales of resolution.

3. DISCUSSION

The preceding discussion and data presented in Table 1 indicate that the vast majority of MSEA languages sampled violate Berlin’s prediction that Generic taxa are labelled by primary names. This is particularly true of plant and fish names, but bird and invertebrate names also present violations, albeit to a lesser degree. The numerous aberrant (from the point of view of Berlin’s predictions) secondary names of Generic taxa incorporate not only the immediately superordinate Life Form labels (as in fish-X or Y-vine), but frequently also the Unique Beginner label (as in Z-plant/plant-Z) in the case of ethnobotanical taxa. Some even have obligatory tripartite names along the lines of plant-fruit-X (similar phenomena are reported by Sellers (2015) and Singnoi (2011) for Lisu and Thai respectively). The data presented here also show that there can be a

range of strategies to name the Generic-level members of different Life Form taxa, within a single language or within a language family. Even Life Form terms (such as ‘tree’) can vary in their construction, with some languages incorporating the Unique Beginner label ‘plant’, resulting in a secondary name along the lines of ‘wood plant’. There are therefore several lines of evidence from MSEA languages to show that the restriction on Generic and Life Form labels being primary names is not a cross-linguistic universal. Further research is needed to determine how many more understudied languages around the world violate this restriction.

An interesting parallel case found outside MSEA is that of the Zapotec languages of Mexico, where plant, mushroom and, optionally, snake names incorporate the superordinate Life Form names, as in *yàg-guiél* (tree-custard.apple), *měy-dùr* (mushroom-pine.needle) and *mèel-ngùbidz* (snake-sun) ‘rattlesnake’ (Hunn 2008). While these are clearly productive secondary names as in our data, Hunn chooses to call them ‘complex primary, but productive names’ (2008:81), so as not to have to rank ‘tree’, ‘herb’, ‘snake’ and ‘mushroom’ as large and complex Generic taxa, and the names listed above as Specifics (Hunn *et al.* 2015). Hunn never states explicitly that the restriction on Generic taxa being labelled with primary names might be violated by his data, and simply concludes that “the plant Generic names are extraordinary” (Hunn 1998, p. 43). While we agree that a label such as *yàg-guiél* (tree-custard.apple) is better ranked as a Generic than a Specific, we feel that Hunn missed a valuable opportunity to dispute an important (and incorrect) nomenclatural constraint with his rich ethnobiological data. Hunn (2008:83) also reports tripartite names (common in Thanau, Bit, Lao, Lisu and Thai, as demonstrated above) as a “striking peculiarity of Gbëë Zapotec plant names”. Such erroneous statements underscore the need for a renewed focus on the typology of ethnobiological classification and nomenclature.

Even though Berlin’s model allows Generics to be labelled by productive primary names, Hunn feels compelled to say that his data are “extraordinary” probably because such names are so numerous in Zapotec. This observation supports our claim (Section 2.1.5) that the model implicitly requires the Generic rank to be dominated by simple primary names like *oak*. The model acknowledges the existence of Generic labels like *tuliptree*, but such complex, productive names are expected to represent a minority of Generic names. The model therefore uses the notion of productive primary names – even though they are linguistically identical to secondary names – simply as an escape hatch to explain inconvenient data points where the Life Form or Unique Beginner label is obligatorily included in the Generic label.

Looking further afield in Mexico, the Zapotec spoken on the Tehuantepec Isthmus shows similar patterns Saynes-Vasquez *et al.* (2016): here too, the Life Form labels *yaga* ‘tree’, *luba* ‘vine’ and *guie* ‘flower’ seem to be obligatorily incorporated into the Generic names. While the authors point out that the

language does not have a lexicalised Unique Beginner (*i.e.* ‘plant’), they do not comment on the mismatch between Berlin’s predictions and the patterns in their own data.

There is evidence to show that binomial Generic labels (at least for plant names) might exist in some languages of South America as well. In the multiethnic, but largely Quichua/Spanish-speaking, community of Canelos in Ecuador, Dodaro (2022, pp. 104-105) appears to report that participants asked to create tree free-lists incorporated the Life Form *ruya* ‘tree’ in all volunteered names, as in *chunchu-ruya* (chunchu-tree) ‘*Cedrelinga cateniformis*’. No such phenomenon was observed for the names of birds or forest animals.

Closer to MSEA, a number of Indian languages also seem to exhibit similar patterns, notably within the Dravidian family. The Solega/Soliga language requires the obligatory Life Form labels *mara* ‘tree’, *ambu* ‘vine’, *giḍa* ‘herb’ and *hullu* ‘grass’ for the vast majority of its ethnobotanical taxa, as in *a:guri-mara* (*a:guri*-tree) ‘*Trema orientalis*’ and the Life Form label *hakki* ‘bird’ for many of its ethno-ornithological taxa, as in *araḷ-akki* (castor-bird) ‘Emerald Dove’ (Si 2016). Similar patterns are evidenced by Tamil as well, *e.g.* *araca-maram* (peepal-tree) ‘*Ficus religiosa*’ (Fabricius 1972).

Finally, Ellen (2020) mentions that in the Nuaulu language of Seram Island, Indonesia, at least 59 are obligate binomials (secondary names) of the form *ai* ‘tree’ + [qualifier], as in *ai osi*. The percentage of such names among the total is difficult to determine, as different figures are provided in the publication, with ambiguous explanations: “Nuaulu recognise and have discrete names for 322 plant taxa ... that we would describe as ‘tree’” (*ibid.*:75), but elsewhere, “Of the 358 terminal plant categories judged to be ‘trees’...” (*ibid.*:85), and also “If we separate all named categories Nuaulu consider to be trees (423)” (*ibid.*:85). This results in a range of 14% to 18% for secondary names in the Nuaulu tree lexicon. The case of the *awane* ‘vine’ Life Form is more straightforward, with 22 out of 44 vine names (50%) containing the elements *wane* or *awane*, either as the first or second element of the binomial. Finally in the case of *unate* ‘mushrooms’¹⁵, practically all Nuaulu mushroom names are constructed in a similar way, *i.e.* as a secondary name, with the contracted first element *una-* signalling the Life Form. Like Hunn, Ellen does not challenge Berlin on this point (though he does point out other departures from the latter’s predictions), and simply states that “*ai* ‘tree’, *awane* ‘vine’, *monote* ‘herb/weed’ are used as prefixes followed by names or qualifying epithets” (*ibid.*:492). The frequency of secondary names in Nuaulu suggests that such Generic labels may actually be widespread in insular southeast Asia as well, but have gone unreported because of undue attention having been paid to theoretical constraints and/or lexicographic conventions. However, the languages of insular southeast Asia mostly belong to the Austronesian family,

¹⁵ Ellen notes that although *unate* appears cognitively to be a Kingdom-level grouping, it functions lexically more like a category of Life Form rank.

and therefore represent a different linguistic region compared to the mainland languages considered in this paper.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In recent years, there have been attempts to move away from the “traditional contrast” or “false opposition” between relativists and universalists (Ludwig 2018, Ellen 2023 respectively), and lead the field of linguistic ethnobiology to more fertile pastures. We welcome this development, but add that there is still a pressing need to determine the extent to which Berlin’s model holds across the world’s languages, using culturally-appropriate cross-linguistic comparisons. Critiquing Berlin’s claims to set the record straight is not the same as taking a strong relativistic stance, although if forced to choose, we would be more comfortable with being labelled “relativists”. Careful investigations of individual claims with the help of data from several (ideally, understudied) languages may well reveal that some of the categorisation- or nomenclature-related constraints are valid for most, if not all languages. They may also show, as we have, that certain constraints do not apply to entire linguistic regions, thereby forcing a purported “universal” to be downgraded to perhaps a “strong trend” or mere “tendency” at a global scale. Cross-linguistic investigations have been carried out in the past (*e.g.* Brown 1984, Wierzbicka 1992), but numerous issues remain unresolved, and as shown above, entire language groupings that may harbour unexpected or contrary features have been neglected in the debate on ethnoclassificatory patterns. This is a worrying situation, as Berlin’s (1992) monograph remains an influential work. Researchers new to the field of ethnobiology may take its pronouncements for granted, and unquestioningly apply them to their own data, resulting in spurious analyses. Ralph Bulmer (1974) had already raised this concern five decades ago, in response to an earlier version of Berlin’s model (Berlin *et al.* 1973):

I do not believe that we can yet demonstrate correspondences between the cognitive statuses of folk taxa and the nomenclature applied to these which are of sufficient intra- and cross-cultural regularity to enable us to arrive at a simple typology. There is an obvious danger in advancing, prematurely, a typology of the kind Dr. Berlin proposes, namely that it may lead ethnographers and lexicographers to distort data by forcing it into inappropriate pigeonholes, and in particular into failing to appreciate and record the degree of flexibility and elasticity which is probably a very general feature of folk taxonomies.

Flexibility and elasticity are clearly evident in the preceding discussion, such as in the case of Bit fish names and Burmese edible plants. Chamberlain (2021) has suggested more recently that cognitive linguistic approaches to categories within biolinguistic systems can shine light on non-taxonomic logic in the animal naming schemes of Tai languages. Other well-known linguistic phenomena such

as language contact, historical change and intra-community variation may also result in unexpected features, and these phenomena need to be taken into account when considering nomenclatural patterns in any given language. The influence of Tai on surrounding Austroasiatic languages has been discussed above. As would be expected, however, convergence resulting from linguistic contact is multidirectional (Matisoff 2019; Enfield 2005). Sesquisyllables in Burmese are a likely influence from Austroasiatic languages (Bradley 1980), evidenced in the fauna terms in the reduction of $\eta\grave{a}$ ‘fish’ to $\eta\partial$ - in fish names; similarly we observe $\eta\acute{a}$ ‘fish’ to $\eta\partial$ - in Asho Chin, suggesting a broader areal phenomenon. Linguistic areas involve mutual influences beyond purely linguistic dynamics (Vittrant and Watkins 2019), and the nomenclature systems discussed above suggest that ecological knowledge is an important related factor. Moreover, there is a valuable opportunity to re-examine the importance of mimetics, sound symbolism and cultural aesthetics in more semiotically nuanced analysis of these nomenclatural systems. The widespread flexibility and elasticity of language in general suggests that straight lexical elicitation methods will often fail to produce reliable data. Field methods that work the intersections of lexicon with syntax, local knowledge and oral practices will better elucidate the type of dynamism that these systems seem to be showing. We hope that the current study will inspire further dispassionate tests of each of Berlin’s claims, in particular by linguist-ethnobiologist teams working to collect contextualised data from under-studied languages in Asia and Africa. The data presented in Table 1 clearly show that there is nothing “extraordinary” about the use of secondary names for Generic taxa in MSEA. Indeed, this pattern can be considered to be the norm. We advocate moving beyond the usual studies on “Ethnoclassification of taxon X in Language L” to also include a cross-linguistic research agenda (especially in areas of high language diversity), where each theoretical constraint is tested separately with data from many languages.

REFERENCES

- Amith, Jonathan. 2020. Endangered language documentation: The challenges of interdisciplinary research in ethnobiology. In Susan Penfield (ed.), *Interdisciplinary approaches to language documentation, language documentation & conservation special publication No. 21*, 72-112. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press.
- Atran, Scott. 1985. The nature of folk-botanical life forms. *American Anthropologist* 87.298-315.
- Atran, Scott. 1999. Itzaj Maya folkbiological taxonomy: cognitive universals and cultural particulars. In Douglas Medin and Scott Atran (eds.), *Folkbiology*, 119-203. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Badenoch, Nathan. 2020. Fishing the uplands: a linguistic perspective on the ethno-ichthyology of Northern Laos. In Hayashi (ed.) *Topics in middle Mekong linguistics* Vol 2, Kobe: Kobe City University of Foreign Studies.
- Badenoch, Nathan. 2021. The ethnopoetics of Sida animal names. In Hayashi (ed.) *Topics in middle Mekong linguistics*. Kobe: Kobe City University of Foreign Studies.
- Berlin, Brent. 1973. Folk systematics in relation to biological classification and nomenclature. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics* 4.259-271.
- Berlin, Brent. 1976. The concept of rank in ethnobiological classification: some evidence from Aguaruna folk botany. *American Ethnologist* 3.381-399.
- Berlin, Brent. 1992. *Ethnobiological classification*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Bradley, David. 1980. Phonological convergence between languages in contact: Mon-Khmer structural borrowing in Burmese. *Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society* 6.259-267.
- Bradley, David. 2006. *Southern Lisu Dictionary*. Berkeley: University of California.
- Brown, Cecil. 1977. Folk botanical life-forms: their universality and growth. *American Anthropologist* 79.317-342.
- Brown, Cecil. 1979. Folk zoological life-forms: their universality and growth. *American Anthropologist* 81.791-817.
- Brown, Cecil. 1984. *Language and living things*. New Brunswick: Rutgers University Press.
- Brown, Cecil. 1985. Mode of subsistence and folk biological taxonomy. *Current Anthropology* 26.43-64.
- Brown, Cecil. 1986. The growth of ethnobiological nomenclature. *Current Anthropology* 27.1-19.
- Bulmer, Ralph. 1974. Folk biology in the New Guinea highlands. *Social Science Information* 13.9-28.
- Chamberlain, James. 1977. *An introduction to Proto-Tai zoology*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan PhD dissertation.

- Chamberlain, James. 1992. Biolinguistic systematics and marking. In *The Third International Symposium on Languages and Linguistics: Pan-Asiatic Linguistics*, Vol. III. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University.
- Chamberlain, James. 2021. Non-taxonomic cognition: classificatory linkages between semantic domains in Tai Languages. *The Journal of Lao Languages* 3.1-10.
- Dodaro, L. 2022. *Intergenerational environmental knowledge transmission as a source of empowerment in a multiethnic indigenous Amazonian community*. New Orleans: Tulane University PhD dissertation.
- Dwyer, Peter. 2005. Ethnobiology, ethnobiology and the imagination. *Journal de la Société des Océanistes* 120-121.12-25.
- Ellen, Roy. 2008. Ethnomycology among the Nuaulu of the Moluccas: putting Berlin's "General Principles" of ethnobiological classification to the test. *Economic Botany* 62.483-496.
- Ellen, Roy. 2020. *The Nuaulu world of plants: ethnobotanical cognition, knowledge and practice among a people of Seram, eastern Indonesia*. Canon Pyon: Sean Kingston.
- Ellen, Roy. 2023. Identifying plants as a process of cultural cognition: comparing knowledge production and communities of practice in modern botanical science and Nuaulu ethnobotany. *Journal of Ethnobiology* 43. 208-218.
- Enfield, Nicholas. 2005. Areal linguistics and mainland Southeast Asia. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 34.181-206.
- Fabricius, Johann. 1972. *Tamil and English Dictionary (4th ed.)* Tranquebar: Evangelical Lutheran Mission Pub. House.
- Forth, Gregory. 2000. Eastern Sumbanese bird classification. *Journal of Ethnobiology* 20.161-192.
- Forth, Gregory. 2003. *Nage Birds*. London: Routledge.
- Forth, Gregory. 2016. *Why the porcupine is not a bird: explorations in the folk zoology of an eastern Indonesian People*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Hays, Terence. 1979. Plant classification and nomenclature in Ndumba, Papua New Guinea Highlands. *Ethnology* 18.253-270.
- Heimbach, Ernest. 1969. *White Hmong-English dictionary*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Hiepko, Paul. 2006. Eipo plant nomenclature and classification compared with other folk taxonomic systems. *Willdenowia* 36.447-453.
- Hunn, Eugene. 1982. The utilitarian factor in folk biological classification. *American Anthropologist* 4.830-847.
- Hunn, Eugene. 1998. Mixtepec Zapotec ethnobiological classification: a preliminary sketch and theoretical commentary. *Anthropologica* 40.35-48.
- Hunn, Eugene. 2008. *A Zapotec natural history: trees, herbs, and flowers, birds, beasts, and bugs in the life of San Juan Gbëë*. Tuscon: University of Arizona Press.

- Hunn, Eugene, Yuliana Ramírez & Marco Dávila. 2015. Where do fungi fit? The fungal domain in Mixtepec Zapotec. *Journal of Ethnobiology* 35.286-313.
- Jenny, Mathias. 2015. Foreign influence in the Burmese language. Paper presented at the International Conference on Burma/Myanmar Studies 'Burma/Myanmar in Transition: Connectivity, Changes and Challenges', Chiangmai, Thailand, 24-25 July, 2015.
- Jenny, Mathias & San San Hnin Tun. 2016. *Burmese: a comprehensive grammar*. London: Routledge.
- Judson, Adoniram. 1893. *Burmese English Dictionary*. Rangoon: Government Printing Burma.
- Kurabe, Keita. 2020. The phonology, morphology, and semantics of Burmese zoonyms. *Journal of Research Institute* 61.65-84.
- Ludwig, David. 2018. Revamping the metaphysics of ethnobiological classification. *Current Anthropology* 59.415-438.
- Mandaville, James. 2004. *Bedouin ethnobotany: plant concepts and plant use in a desert pastoral world*. Tuscon: University of Arizona PhD dissertation.
- Martin, Gary. 2010. *Ethnobotany: A Methods Manual*. London: Routledge.
- Matisoff, James. 2006. *English-Lahu lexicon*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Matisoff, James. 2011. Areal and universal issues in plant and animal nomenclature. *Bulletin of the National Museum of Ethnology* 35.655-679.
- Matisoff, James. 2019. Preface. In Alice Vittrant & Justin Watkins (eds.) *The Mainland Southeast Asia Linguistic Area*. Berlin: de Gruyter/Mouton.
- McClatchey, Will. 2011. Ethnobiology: Basic methods for documenting biological knowledge represented in languages. In Nicholas Thieberger (ed.) *The Oxford Handbook of Linguistic Fieldwork*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Myanmar Language Commission. 2013. *Myanmar-English Dictionary*. Yangon: Myanmar Language Commission.
- Randall, Robert & Eugene Hunn. 1984. Do life-forms evolve or do uses for life? Some doubts about Brown's universals hypotheses. *American Ethnologist* 11.329-349.
- Rattanapitak, Ampika. 2009. Palaung wordlist. *Journal of Language and Culture* 28.77-122.
- Scott, Gerald. 2000. *A traditional Lakota zoological folk taxonomy*. DeKalb: Northern Illinois University PhD dissertation.
- SEAlang. 2007a. *SEAlang library Khmer dictionary*. <https://sealang.net/khmer/dictionary.htm> (Accessed 01-11-2023).
- SEAlang. 2007b. *SEAlang library Lao dictionary*. <https://sealang.net/lao/dictionary.htm> (Accessed 01-11-2023).
- SEAlang. 2009a. *SEAlang library Mon dictionary*. <https://sealang.net/mon/dictionary.htm> (Accessed 01-11-2023).

- SEAlang. 2009b. *SEAlang library Vietnamese dictionary*. <https://sealang.net/vietnamese/dictionary.htm> (Accessed 01-11-2023).
- Saynes-Vásquez, Alfredo, Francisco Vergara-Silva, & Javier Caballero. 2016. An interdisciplinary perspective on the loss of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) in the Tehuantepec Isthmus, Oaxaca. In Rafael Lira, Alejandro Cajas & Jose Blancas (eds.) *Ethnobotany of Mexico: Interactions of People and Plants in Mesoamerica*, 457-473. New York: Springer.
- Sellers, Holly. 2015. *A linguistic approach to plant name classification in Lisu*. Melbourne: LaTrobe University PhD dissertation.
- Si, Aung. 2014. Danau. In Mathias Jenny & Paul Sidwell (eds.) *The handbook of Austroasiatic languages*, 1104-1141. Leiden: Brill.
- Si, Aung. 2016. *The traditional ecological knowledge of the Solega: a linguistic perspective*. Cham: Springer.
- Si, Aung & Aung Kyawphyo. 2023. Patterns in fish naming ability in two fishing communities of Myanmar. *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine* 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13002-023-00610-7>.
- Sillitoe, Paul. 2002. Contested knowledge, contingent classification: animals in the highlands of Papua New Guinea. *American Anthropologist* 104.1162-1171.
- Singnoi, Unchalee. 2011. A reflection of Thai culture in Thai plant names. *Manusya: Journal of Humanities* 14.79-97.
- Svantesson, Jan-Olof, Kàm Raw, Kristina Lindell and Håkan Lundström. 2014. *Dictionary of Kammu Yùan language and culture*. Copenhagen: NIAS Press.
- Valenzuela, Pilar. 2000. Major categories in Shipibo ethnobiological taxonomy. *Anthropological Linguistics* 42.1-36.
- Vidal, Jules. 1959. Noms vernaculaires de plantes (lao, mèo, kha) en usage au Laos. *Bulletin de l'Ecole Française d'Extrême-Orient* 49.435-608.
- Vidal, Jules. 1963. Systématique, nomenclature et phytonymie botanique populaire au Laos. *Journal d'Agriculture Tropicale et de Botanique Appliquée* 10.438-448.
- Vittrant, Alice and Justin Watkins. 2019. Introduction: Languages of the mainland Southeast Asia linguistic area - grammatical sketches. In Alice Vittrant & Justin Watkins (eds.) *The Mainland Southeast Asia Linguistic Area*. Berlin: de Gruyter/Mouton.
- Watkins, J. 2013. *Dictionary of Wa, with translations into English, Burmese and Chinese*. Leiden: Brill.
- Wierzbicka, Anna. 1984. "Apples" are not a "kind of fruit". *American Ethnologist* 11, 313-328.
- Wierzbicka, Anna. 1992. What is a life form? Conceptual issues in ethnobiology. *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology* 2.3-29.